

ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

A model of manufacturing is proposed based on microeconomic theory. The model is defined as having all external attributes pre-defined by the owning firm. The model of manufacturing is then analyzed as a closed system. The model is further defined as having products and resources of pure monetary value. The model uses the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution (MRTS) to formulate opportunity costs and marginal profits for each product. Precise calculations of opportunity cost allows the model to be self-constraining, without requiring external constraints to narrow the scope of the model. A methodology is presented, based on the microeconomic model, that uses an iterative search to determine product quantities that provide optimum profit. A software utility is created to automate the methodology. The software implementation is modular, allows piece-wise linear descriptions of products and resources, and provides the facility for approximating product descriptions from theoretical microeconomic types using the techniques of fuzzy logic.

NORTHERN ILLINOIS UNIVERSITY

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fulfillment of degree requirements.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Motivation

The profit potential of manufactured goods is dependent upon market forces derived from the microeconomic forms of competition, monopoly, and their intermediate types. Within a single manufacturer, similar microeconomic forms pervade the product groupings selected for production.

Products can be viewed within manufacturing as competing both for resources and an internal market share. Products and their production lines exist as though competing firms within a market defined by the manufacturing situation itself. Products can be judged by their relationship to their resource needs, availability of resources, their interrelationships to one another, and their strategic potential. Microeconomic forms readily apply to all of these product attributes.

Similarities of manufacturing and microeconomics can be exploited to use the constructs of microeconomics to analyze and optimize the profit potential of manufacturing. The strategic potential of a product is determined by the manufacturer, with or without regard to the actual market forces under which the manufacturer operates. A manufacturer deems a product *strategically* competitive even if its actual marketing form is monopolistic when it finds the need to create a market niche for the product or to satisfy the desires of an important customer. In this case, the manufacturer may use the microeconomic notion of *subsidy* on the product.

Production quantity is a vital parameter in the profit equation. Predicting the optimum quantity of a product to generate involves a complex function of resource needs, anticipated scrap and rework, opportunity costs, and potential revenue, all with regard to equivalent evaluations of quantities for competing products. The opportunity costs themselves create a complex association between product profit potentials and wasted resources (scrap and rework).

Opportunity cost is a product attribute not only of disregarded alternate capital investments, but also of foregone revenue caused by failing to apply resource investments to other products. Each resource has a revenue potential with a value dependent upon the final product. If the resources are lost by scrap or rework, the opportunity costs are reflected in the value of the resources that could have been applied to the next lucrative product.

The typical methods used to evaluate complex systems, like the manufacture of various products, consist of mathematical models glued together by Boolean decisions. The overall evaluation is based on strict, concise, and invariant rules that try to anticipate the real artifacts of a system. The manufacturing system is not, however, strict, concise, and invariant; the real artifacts of manufacturing contain ambivalent aspects that Boolean definitions only vaguely approximate. The defining variables in actual manufacturing, and their requisite equations, tend toward a qualitative vagueness rather than a quantitative exactitude. A manufacturer's edict is more likely to be "make more while profits are good" than "produce another 1500 while revenue is \$18.00 per unit and cost is under \$10.00 per unit". A manufacturer knows that *making more* will increase revenue with more certitude than knowing the effect of producing another 1500. Linguistic terms rather than numerical absolutes pervade manufacturing. Linguistic terms coincide with the essential aspects of the manufacturing system. Numerical certainty and Boolean decisions are artificially exact; they

are *approximations* of system parameters and require elaborate tests of correctness within the model itself to generate a reasonable degree of confidence [Kosko, 1993].

Modeling a manufacturing system with microeconomic forms is a straightforward approach to gauge optimal production quantities. Applying linguistic variables in the form of *fuzzy logic* to the model parameters of the manufacturing system allows simple representations instead of elaborate, complex, and potentially unstable mathematical estimations of the parameters. Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing can yield accurate product evaluation with relatively simple analogues of system components.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The essential value of manufacturing needs to be gauged to the profit of the owning firm. To do this, the essential nature of manufacturing must be described in precise and quantifiable terms.

A manufacturing system can be described simply as inputs and outputs. The inputs are resources and the outputs are products. A manufacturing facility requires access to appropriate resources to build products; likewise, products must match the manufacturing capability of the facility. The products capable of being manufactured at a particular facility make up a finite product set. An owning firm expects certain products from its manufacturing facilities and these comprise a subset of the aforementioned product set; this subset is the *Product Domain* and all the resources that are required by the product domain comprise the *Resource Domain*.

A product's utility to its owning firm is in its ability to add to the firm's overall profit. A *priority of utility* within a product domain can be determined by evaluating the resource costs and selling prices of products in relation to one another. If how the individual

elements of the product domain provides utility to the system can be determined, that is, how overall utility is distributed among the target products, the capital attributes of the target set can be manipulated to maximize utility. The system can then be brought into *microeconomic equilibrium*, where each member of the product domain is equally effective to supporting the overall system profit.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to formulate a methodology that satisfies the following five primary goals. The first goal is to show that a manufacturing system can be modeled as a closed microeconomic system defined by its own resource domain and its own product domain. A closed system means that all external parameters are pre-defined and static and the system itself provides constraints internally.

The second goal is to determine the individual quantities of a set of target products that most nearly produces microeconomic equilibrium. That is, determine the quantities of each product that makes each product equally valuable to the system.

The third goal is to determine the selling prices of products that most nearly create microeconomic equilibrium for a set of target products.

The fourth goal is to determine the resource costs that would most nearly create microeconomic equilibrium for a set of target products.

The fifth goal is to define an implementation in software that embodies the methodology and allows the user the ability to satisfy the first four goals.

1.4 Assumptions

The study is based on five assumptions. First, it is assumed that the owning firm defines the market within which manufacturing operates, including the resource and product domains. The owning firm provides the information concerning product types and product pricing as well as resource types and their costs. The information may or may not be derived externally from the firm depending upon particular strategies the firm wishes to pursue. This assumption qualifies the proposed model as a closed model.

All resources are viewed as having interchangeable capital value that is infinitely divisible; that is, the value in one or a set of resources can be transformed directly into other resources either partially or completely.

In calculating the opportunity cost (OC) of a product, the minor adjustments to the product quantities (and resource quantities) that would occur from producing the alternate product instead of the target product are assumed to have negligible effect on the pricing structure of the competing product or its resources.

The price (cost) versus quantity descriptions of products and resources are assumed to be accurately estimated by a piece-wise linear function described by a set of discrete points.

The quantities demanded of a product are requirements of the owning firm and any quantities demanded are completely sellable.

1.5 Organization of the Study

This study is organized around the application of microeconomic theory to manufacturing. Microeconomic theory is reviewed, identifying a model of manufacturing as a closed

system that has strong resemblance to a capital market. A market contains inputs and outputs, each with its own pricing structure and profit; the manufacture of products maintains similar influences of its resources and products. Market transformations are made on the *value* of consumable resources into the *value* of products of manufacture; these transformations result in a basic utility of products to the profit of the owning firm.

This research takes concepts directly from microeconomics to form analogous ideas that describe manufacturing attributes. The notions of opportunity cost and marginal profit become discernible, mathematical formulations of a manufacturing system.

The description of a product and its required resources is regarded in two ways: 1) by directly applying historical data in the form of an *a priori* pricing function of demand, or 2) using fuzzy logic and information from experts to modify the theoretical curves of the standard microeconomic product types. The two methods of describing a product are analytical and procedural, respectively. The analytical approach is contrasted with the procedural approach, identifying the cases where one method favors the other in regard to actual usefulness and accuracy. Fuzzy logic is reviewed as the procedural approach.

All concepts are put together to form a methodology that allows analysis and optimization of a manufacturing system without having to explicitly constrain the manufacturing model. The methodology is used to formulate an algorithm and then a direct application in software of a microeconomic model of manufacturing.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Subjects Related to Topic

A model of manufacturing is defined as a closed microeconomic system defined by a resource domain and a product domain. A model of manufacturing is proposed that allows manufacturing to be viewed and analyzed as a market in and of itself. The literature to strengthen this proposition needs to combine a few, pivotal concepts drawn from the subjects that are typically utilized independently.

Existing literature germane to the research can be classified under four primary groups: microeconomics, engineering economy, manufacturing, and fuzzy logic. The focus of this research is to combine three main groups: microeconomics, manufacturing, and fuzzy logic.

2.2 Summary of Existing Literature

A literature search of the aforementioned subjects was performed, though it was difficult to locate any instance of linking the three main items together. There were several articles that blended the topic of Fuzzy Logic with Manufacturing. There was one relevant article that used microeconomics with manufacturing [Jewkes, 1993]; the few remaining articles that contained Economics and Manufacturing together merely identify external economic factors of manufacturing, rather than pursuing a model of some aspect of manufacturing in economic (or microeconomic) terms.

The following is a review of the articles found most pertinent to the subject of this research.

[Jewkes, 1993] develops a limited microeconomic model of a JIT manufacturing system. All inputs are treated as monopsonies and all outputs are treated as competitive. The author uses microeconomics to show the benefits of JIT manufacturing. Targeting a JIT manufacturing system and employing a narrow assumption of the microeconomic character of resources and outputs greatly limits the general applicability intended by this research. General manufacturing systems have resources and outputs that vary greatly in their supply and demand characteristics.

[Dhillon, 1995] explores the use of fuzzy set theory to enhance decisions based on the stochastic nature of production costs and of product demand. A selection methodology is developed for optimizing among many objectives that are of a stochastic nature. A fuzzy logic approach is also used to refine “the classical economic dispatch problem” for limited resources. The relevance of this article to this research is limited to the use of fuzzy set theory to reasonably quantify “non-commensurable objectives” of costs and demand mismatches.

[Koyama, 1995] describes the use of fuzzy logic in controlling outgoing quality and increasing product throughput. The author explores controlling quantities by analyzing both fuzzy and statistical information about the incoming and outgoing quality of products. This article has some direct relevance to one aspect of this research, since fuzzy logic techniques akin to system control are incorporated into the overall plan of this research.

Setting target attributes in a systematic way for products is the focus of [Nikolaidis, 1995]. The author proposes the use of fuzzy logic to appropriately target attributes of new products; that is, evaluating the costs of targeting specific performance characteristics. Relevance of

this article to this research is in the general description of fuzzy logic as a vehicle to describe key attributes of a product.

[Wang, X.Z., 1995] describes fuzzy modeling of process systems using directed graphs. Fuzzy logic is used to substitute for an analytical model of a system; this use of fuzzy logic is typical in the fuzzy control of complex systems and it will be used in the software utility borne by this research. The research is limited to one aspect and use of fuzzy logic theory and therefore has only partial relevance to one objective of this research.

[Wang, M.J.J., 1995] describes using fuzzy sets for a multi-criteria decision making system in steel manufacturing. The use of fuzzy logic to implement linguistic values is described. Similar to [Wang, X.Z., 1995], it is limited to one aspect and use of fuzzy logic theory, only partially relevant to one objective of this research.

Failure mechanisms in manufacturing steps using fuzzy logic are evaluated by [Bazu, 1995]. Fuzzy logic is narrowly used in the article to implement fuzzy parameters as analytical coefficients. The application of fuzzy logic in the article is similar to the use of fuzzy set theory in this research.

Other research explores the use of fuzzy logic in manufacturing [Cios, 1995], present a simplified technique for fuzzy control of processes [Kouatli, 1994][Turksen, 1994], describes the use of fuzzy logic in quality decisions that have varying criteria of costs and flexibility [Gutierrez, 1995], and describes the use of fuzzy set theory to determine consumer choice [Turksen, 1994]. All of this research has similar relevance to this thesis and are comparable to the articles above that refer to the use of fuzzy logic.

One author presents the subject of economics with manufacturing [Lin, 1995], another, economics with fuzzy logic [Matloka, 1993]. Both authors limit their discussions to macro-economic evaluation of profitability of a system per se. The use of microeconomics in this research is in modeling *attributes* of a manufacturing system, not evaluating the economic potential of the system to an external market.

[Weigel, 1993] gives a moderately analytical view of opportunity cost; often, analytical definitions of opportunity cost rely on potential interest capital from the value of an item. Other definitions are often less useful in direct application, being too general and intangible for use in a particular analysis. In this dissertation, opportunity cost is derived from the average income of typical replacement of the target item.

[Kim, 1993] presents opportunity cost as both capital and non-capital losses. Results for the *quality* of the opportunity costs are derived empirically from surveys.

2.3 Voids and Needs of the Existing Literature

Absent from the current literature is a conceptualization of manufacturing as a self-actualizing entity that can be modeled as a closed system of interacting elements of monetary value. Every aspect of manufacturing does have a monetary value that affects the overall profitability of the owning firm. All elements of manufacturing can have relative freedom to seek optimal levels of capacity to maintain or enhance overall profit, much like buyers and sellers in a microeconomic market.

Fuzzy logic, as an applied technique, is not utilized in very many disciplines, particularly the social sciences. However, the procedural method embodied by the technique is well suited to disciplines like microeconomics, where much of the data used in analysis is

empirical, linguistic, and given to substantial human bias of both the subjects and the administrator of the analysis.

This research will amplify the use of fuzzy logic as an analytical tool that is particularly useful in microeconomic modeling. This research will also enhance the existing literature by applying microeconomic theory to manufacturing, providing a simple and straightforward linkage between the two disciplines.

CHAPTER 3

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Microeconomics

3.1.1 Review

Exchanges between producers and consumers of goods are naturally enabled by markets. The market prices of goods are determined by exchanges and interactions of buyers and sellers, by the number of goods made, bought, and sold [Quirk, 1987].

Manufacturing is then a market that facilitates exchanges between products, acting as buyers and sellers of goods (resources), and these interactions determine the prices of products and the costs of resources by virtue of the quantities demanded and consumed. The interaction between consuming and producing products are described succinctly by using standard product typing.

Microeconomic theory defines four basic product types: *perfect competition*, *competitive-monopoly*, *oligopoly*, and *monopoly*. Perfect competition (or simply, competition) and monopoly are the limiting types; competitive-monopoly and oligopoly derive characteristics from both. In a perfectly competitive market, firms are essentially units of manufacturing that take inputs and create outputs. Every participant is a *price taker* rather than a *price maker* [Quirk, 1987]. And at the other end of the microeconomic spectrum is the monopoly, where the market has one manufacturer that behaves as a *price maker*.

The basic structure of microeconomic analysis develops from the interrelationship of monetary value and the quantity demanded of the object of this value, that is, the revenue achieved by a specific sellable quantity of a product.

The average revenue (AR) as a function of quantity demanded (Q) is defined as:

$$AR(Q) = TR(Q)/Q \quad (3-1)$$

where Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
 AR is the average revenue
 TR is the total revenue

The marginal revenue (MR) describes the ratio of the change in revenue due to a corresponding change in quantity:

$$MR(Q) = \Delta TR(Q) / \Delta Q \quad (3-2)$$

where MR is the marginal revenue
 TR is the total revenue
 Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
 ΔQ is the change in quantity produced (demanded)
 ΔR is the change in the total resources consumed

Profit maximization for a monopoly occurs when the cost of producing the next unit reaches a value equivalent to the revenue received by that unit. Of course, this is true for any product type. What makes a monopoly different is that the demand curve for a monopoly is also its average revenue (AR) curve and its marginal revenue (MR) curve is modified accordingly (for a perfectly competitive product, the average and marginal revenues are the same as the selling price).

Average revenue must be greater than the average variable cost (AVC) for a monopoly to continue production [Quirk, 1987].

A monopoly's demand for resources is the same as that for any other product type, since the product type is only descriptive of a manufacturer's output, not the inputs that support it.

Revenue is maximum where the demand for a product has a one to one correspondence with a change in selling price and the marginal revenue is zero (the total revenue (TR) curve has zero slope). For small, finite changes in Q (i.e., ΔQ),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MR} &= \Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q \\ &= (p\Delta Q + Q\Delta p) / \Delta Q \\ &= p + Q\Delta p / \Delta Q \end{aligned} \tag{3-3}$$

where MR is the marginal revenue
 p is the selling price
 Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
 ΔTR is the total revenue

$p\Delta Q$ is the increase in revenue due to the increase in quantity sold; $Q\Delta p$ is the decrease (Δp is a negative change in price) in revenue due to the need to lower selling price to increase quantity sold; their sum is the change in total revenue, ΔTR .

3.1.2 Marginal Revenue and Elasticity of Demand

The relationship between quantity produced and revenue as a function of the quantity produced increases or decreases depending upon the elasticity of the demand curve; that is, how changeable the quantity demanded of a product is to the change in its selling price. If the demand is elastic, then increased quantity translates into increased marginal revenue (though lower selling price); an inelastic demand curve means that a increasing quantity translates to a decrease in marginal revenue (and a lower selling price); if the demand curve is unit elastic, changes in quantity cause no change in marginal revenue [Quirk, 1987].

Moreover, as the total revenue (TR) curve (see Figure 1) for a product displays, there are three possibilities for its slope that correspond directly to the product's elasticity of demand. That is, a zero slope indicates a unit elasticity of demand; a negative slope, an elasticity of demand that is less than one; a positive slope, an elasticity greater than one [Chacholiades, 1986].

The price elasticity of demand, η , is an important indicator in microeconomics since it shows the responsiveness to price of the quantity demanded of a product. η can be elastic, in-elastic, or unity elastic and is derived by [Quirk, 1986][Chacholiades, 1987]:

$$\eta = \frac{\text{price}}{\text{Demand}(\text{price})} \cdot \frac{d\text{Demand}(\text{price})}{d\text{price}} \quad (3-4)$$

Where η is the price elasticity of demand
 $d\text{Demand}$ is the derivative of the demand curve, $\text{Demand}(\text{price})$
 price is the product selling price
 $d\text{price}$ is the derivative of the price of the product

For finite changes in quantity, η , is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= (\Delta Q / \Delta p)(p/Q) \\ MR &= (\Delta p / \Delta Q)Q + p \\ (\Delta p / \Delta Q) &= (1/\eta)(p/Q) \\ MR &= (1/\eta)(p/Q)Q + p = p(1/\eta + 1) \end{aligned} \quad (3-5)$$

When $\eta = -1$, $MR = 0 \leftarrow$ unit elastic demand
 When $-1 < \eta < 0$, $MR < 0 \leftarrow$ inelastic demand
 When $\eta < -1$, $MR > 0 \leftarrow$ elastic demand

Where η is the price elasticity of demand
 MR is the marginal revenue; ΔQ is the change in quantity;
 Δp is the change in price; Q is the total quantity; p is the total price

Figure 1: Total Revenue Curve

With a downward sloping demand curve (Average Revenue curve of Figure 1), as there is with a monopoly or monopolist-competition, $\eta \leq 0$; therefore the marginal revenue is less than the selling price ($MR < P$) for a monopoly or monopolistic-competition or any product type with a downward sloping average revenue curve [Quirk, 1987][Brown, 1992].

Microeconomic theory includes the idea that similar products may be demanded very differently by consumers. This idea takes form in the notions of *normal* and *inferior* goods. A normal good is a product that continues in demand as the available capital of the

consumer increases. An *inferior* good is a product that has less demand as available consumer capital increases [Brown, 1992].

Within manufacturing, products are viewed as goods that support the owning firm's profit. That is, products are inputs that manufacturing transforms into outputs that take the form of an incremental profit. Some products may be normal goods, always providing profit regardless of quantities produced and regardless of the competing products being manufactured. Other products may be inferior goods that provide a level of profit for small quantities, but less profit than a competing product at some higher quantity of production. Often, a product that is a normal good may substitute for a product that behaves as an inferior good to the overall profit of a manufacturing system.

3.1.3 Opportunity Cost

In a system of products, the value of each product (the *marginal utility*, MU) in regard to the marginal cost (the *unit cost*, UC) of that product gives the marginal utility per unit cost of the product (the *Product Utility*, PU):

$$PU_i = \frac{MU_i}{UC_i} \quad (3-6)$$

Where PU_i is the Product Utility of product i
 MU_i is the Marginal Utility of product i
 UC_i is the unit cost of product i

The Product Utility is similar to the microeconomic notion of the Marginal Product of a resource; the Marginal Product is the ratio of product output change to the resource change that produced the difference in output. For example, the change in output from x to y units, due to a z increase in labor, gives a (y-x)/z Marginal Product of Labor, denoted as MP_L . The Product Utility gives the unit change in output (in monetary value) to the total resource cost of producing the unit of product.

The rate at which one product is replaceable by another is given by the ratio of their product utilities; this is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution (MRTS). In microeconomic theory the MRTS is the ratio of Marginal Products (say, labor, L, and machines, M, denoted by : $MRTS = MP_L / MP_M$) for the same product[Quirk, 1986][Brown, 1992]; here, the MRTS is used to denote the ratio of the Product Utility (which is analogous to the Marginal Product) of two different products within the same system. The MRTS measures of the substitutability of one product for another:

$$MRTS_{ij} = \frac{PU_i}{PU_j} = \frac{MU_i \cdot UC_j}{MU_j \cdot UC_i} \quad (3- 7)$$

Where $MRTS_{ij}$ is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution for product i in regard to product j
 PU_i is the Product Utility of product i
 MU_i is the Marginal Utility of product i
 UC_i is the unit cost of product i

The marginal utility (MU) of a product is its revenue potential, or selling price, P. So, the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution is formulated as:

$$MRTS_{ij} = \frac{P_i \cdot UC_j}{P_j \cdot UC_i} \quad (3- 8)$$

Where $MRTS_{ij}$ is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution for product i in regard to product j
 P_i is the selling price of product i
 UC_i is the unit cost of product i

Opportunity Cost (OC) is the revenue foregone by not employing the *value* of the resources used to make one product in making an alternate product. The alternate product is one that must achieve the greatest value to the system (or the next greatest value, if the current product already provides the most value). The product potential, when using the value of

resources from another product, is $MRTS_{ji} \cdot P_i = P_j \cdot \frac{UC_i}{UC_j}$. The (marginal) Opportunity

Cost is calculated as:

$$OC_i = MRTS_{ji} \cdot P_i - UC_i$$

Note: the total resource cost (UC_i) is deducted from the potential revenue ($MRTS_{ji} \cdot P_i$) to obtain the net opportunity cost.

$$OC_i = \left(\frac{P_j \cdot UC_i}{P_i \cdot UC_j} \right) \cdot P_i - UC_i = \left(\frac{P_j \cdot UC_i}{UC_j} \right) - UC_i \quad (3-9)$$

Where OC_i is the Opportunity cost of product i by not building product j

$MRTS_{ij}$ is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution for product i in regard to product j

P_i is the selling price of product i

UC_i is the unit cost of product i

3.1.4 Marginal Profit

For every unit of product produced, the Marginal Profit (MP) within the product domain is the selling price less the cost of the resources used less the opportunity cost:

$$\begin{aligned} MP_i &= P_i - OC_i - UC_i = P_i - \left(P_j \cdot \left(\frac{UC_i}{UC_j} \right) - UC_i \right) - UC_i \\ &= P_i - P_j \cdot \left(\frac{UC_i}{UC_j} \right) \left[= P_i \cdot (1 - MRTS_{ji}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3-10)$$

Where MP_i is the Marginal Profit of product i

OC_i is the Opportunity cost of product i by not building product j

P_i and UC_i are the selling price and unit cost of product i

$MRTS_{ji}$ is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution (product i in regard to product j)

The marginal profit is the slope of the profit curve; when the marginal profit is zero, the profit is at an extremum and when this extremum is approached from the rising side of the

profit curve, the extreme point is the point of maximum profit. Beyond the point of zero *marginal* profit, total profit will diminish. Of course, the extremum may only be a local one; others may emerge for another set of product quantities.

When all products within the product domain have reached the point of zero marginal profits, the system is in *microeconomic equilibrium*.

When a product has a negative marginal profit, it has an inefficient selling price and/or inefficient use of resources. When a product has a positive marginal profit it has an *over* efficient selling price and/or *over* efficient use of resources. Efficiency, of course, is in regard to other products in the system of products. All products within system that are in equilibrium have efficient selling prices and use resources efficiently.

Total profit for a product is proportional to the quantity sold, and is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} Pr_i &= \sum_i Q_i \cdot P_i \cdot (1 - MRTS_{ji}), \text{ for all } j \\ &= \sum_i Q_i \cdot (P_i - UC_i) \end{aligned} \quad (3- 11)$$

Where Pr_i is the total profit for product i
 Q_i is the total quantity sold of product i
 P_i is the selling price of product i
 UC_i is the unit cost of producing product i
 $MRTS_{ji}$ is the Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution for j

3.2 The Product Mix Problem

The following features characterize a product mix problem:

1. Maximization of contribution to profit and overhead.
2. Constraints resulting from resource limitations.
3. Bound constraints on planned production.¹

The standard product mix Linear Programming (LP) model (for n products and m resources) is:

$$\max Z = \sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - UC_i) Q_i \quad (3-12)$$

$$\text{Subject to } \sum_{j=1}^m q_{j,i} r_j \leq R_i ; i = 1..n$$

$$Q_i \geq Q \min_i ; i = 1..n$$

$$Q_i \leq Q \max_i ; i = 1..n$$

Where Q_i is the quantity produced of product i
 $q_{j,i}$ is the quantity of resource i used in product j
 p_i is the price of product i
 UC_i is the unit cost of product i
 r_j is the cost of resource j
 R_i is the total resources availability for resource i

The subject of this research is somewhat related to a product mix problem in that a way to optimize manufacturing is formulated. The product mix problem attempts optimization with predefined resource constraints; however, the microeconomic model of this research does not require explicit constraints. The constraints of the microeconomic model are subtle and reside within the defined prices and costs of the products themselves and their interrelated value to the overall profit. The key element that constrains the microeconomic model is opportunity cost, which the microeconomic model uses to explore and force a state of equilibrium within the system of products.

¹ Johnson, Lynwood A., Douglas C. Montgomery. *Operations Research in Production Planning, Scheduling, and Inventory Control*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, New York 1974, 107-109.

A consequential characteristic of microeconomic equilibrium is that each product provides the same effect to the overall profit in regard to the value of the resources that are consumed in the manufacture of each product. Moving the manufacture of a set of products toward microeconomic equilibrium optimizes manufacturing utility and profit.

Where the microeconomic model differs from the product mix problem, apart from not requiring explicit resource constraints, is in the evaluation of marginal changes in quantity. Variations in the quantity of products cause dynamic fluctuations in the manufacturing parameters, affecting both product prices and resource costs. In this regard, the product mix problem is actually a static problem that regards pricing and costs as constants.

3.2.1 Goal Programming Example

Using the microeconomic model, each change in quantity can be evaluated using a modified linear program in the form of a *goal program* [Winston, 1995].

A goal program for the microeconomic model sets the target parameter for each product as part of the objective function (3-13). Each execution of the goal program yields optimum values for a particular, static value set of system variables (resource costs, for example). Evaluating several goal programs, modifying (or *evolving*) the product quantities in each, gives a more accurate description of the manufacturing system than a single evaluation yields.

$$\text{MAX } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n U_i + \sum_{i=1}^n O_i \quad (3-13)$$

Subject To

$$f(P_1) - U_1 + O_1 \leftarrow \text{constraint 1}$$

$$f(P_2) - U_2 + O_2 \leftarrow \text{constraint 2}$$

.

.

.

$$f(P_n) - U_n + O_n \leftarrow \text{Constraint n}$$

Where Z is the objective function

P_i is the target parameter for product i

n is the number of products in the system

U_i is the acceptable negative variation of $f(P_i)$ from 0

O_i is the acceptable positive variation of $f(P_i)$ from 0

All variables have values ≥ 0

The following is assumed for the example: all resource costs are constant; there are four resources in the resource domain and the product domain consists of four products. Initially, pricing is not set for any product, but the largest selling price for product #1 is \$9.50.

The example goal is: at what selling prices should the products be set?

Resource cost are: $R_1 = \$1.50$, $R_2 = \$0.75$, $R_3 = \$3.20$, $R_4 = \$1.75$

Product prices are: P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4

The unit costs (UC's) for the system of products product is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{UC}_1 &= R_1 + 3R_2 + 2R_4 = \$7.25 \\ \text{UC}_2 &= 2R_2 + R_3 + R_4 = \$6.45 \\ \text{UC}_3 &= R_1 + R_2 + R_3 + 2R_4 = \$8.94 \\ \text{UC}_4 &= 3R_3 + 4R_4 = \$16.60 \end{aligned}$$

The most and next most profitable products must first be determined so that marginal profits can be accurately calculated and optimized for each product. A *goal program* is executed, using product #1 and product #2 as the most and next most profitable products and using the results for ranking the profitability within the product domain. Then the LP program is run an additional time, using the appropriate “best” and “next best” products.

For the initial LP model, the marginal profits are:

$$\begin{aligned} MP_1 &= P_1 - P_2*(UC_1/UC_2) = P_1 - 1.124*P_2 \\ MP_2 &= P_2 - P_1*(UC_2/UC_1) = P_2 - 0.8897*P_1 \\ MP_3 &= P_3 - P_1*(UC_3/UC_1) = P_3 - 1.2345*P_2 \\ MP_4 &= P_4 - P_1*(UC_4/UC_1) = P_4 - 2.2897*P_2 \end{aligned}$$

From the iterative search output in Appendix I (listing 1), the optimal solution of the initial LP program allows us to rank the product in order of most profit potential:

$$\begin{aligned} P_4 &\rightarrow 100.0000 \text{ (Profit} = \$100.00 - \$16.60 = \$83.40) \\ P_3 &\rightarrow 53.9108 \text{ (Profit} = \$53.91 - \$8.95 = \$44.96) \\ P_1 &\rightarrow 43.6782 \text{ (Profit} = \$43.68 - \$7.25 = \$36.43) \\ P_2 &\rightarrow 38.8605 \text{ (Profit} = \$38.86 - \$6.45 = \$32.41) \end{aligned}$$

The marginal profit calculations are then revised according to the adjusted product ranking:

$$\begin{aligned} MP_1 &= P_1 - P_4*(U_1/U_4) = P_1 - 0.4367*P_4 \\ MP_2 &= P_2 - P_4*(U_2/U_4) = P_2 - 0.3886*P_4 \\ MP_3 &= P_3 - P_4*(U_3/U_4) = P_3 - 0.5392*P_3 \\ MP_4 &= P_4 - P_3*(U_4/U_3) = P_4 - 2.5736*P_4 \end{aligned}$$

From the iterative search output in Appendix I (listing 2), the equilibrium prices are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Product \#1} &\rightarrow P_1 = \$9.50 \text{ (Unit Profit} = \$ 2.25) \\ \text{Product \#2} &\rightarrow P_2 = \$8.46 \text{ (Unit Profit} = \$ 2.01) \\ \text{Product \#3} &\rightarrow P_3 = \$11.73 \text{ (Unit Profit} = \$ 2.78) \\ \text{Product \#4} &\rightarrow P_4 = \$21.78 \text{ (Unit Profit} = \$ 5.18) \end{aligned}$$

3.2.2 Difficulties with Static Evaluations

In the previous example all resources were held constant. The costs of actual resources will usually be functions of the total quantity consumed (purchased). In a real analysis of a system of products, the costs of some resources must be varied. The marginal profit calculation is linear as long as the total resource requirement of each product can be considered constant; that is, linear programming can be used by examining the system at all resources and product prices for specific product quantities demanded.

The problem with employing standard LP techniques concerns two procedural elements: 1) real manufacturing systems are often non-linear, requiring several finite linear permutations and the analysis of each permutation. 2) Every modification in an LP model of a manufacturing system is unique and must be rewritten and re-executed for each modification.

3.3 Stochastic Elements

The price of a manufactured product depends upon the quantity demanded of the product. This is true unless the product is a perfectly competitive one. Variability in the demand of a product means uncertainty in the amount of the product that should be produced.

Gauging uncertainty for product demand is difficult when dealing with problems containing constraints, whether the constraints are explicitly defined, as in the product mix problem, or inherent to the model, as in the microeconomic model of manufacturing. Typically, maximum demands for products are specified. Error probability distributions can be used that are associated with the particular method of determining demand; this provides a reasonably objective confidence interval of the maximum (or minimum) product quantities. Since there is a normal bias against overproduction, some subjective judgments and measures are also in any derived confidence interval.

A so called Chance-Constrained Model [Johnson, 1974] uses the normal distribution to anticipate a confidence interval for demand, assuming the demand forecast error is normally distributed. The upper demand limit for the model is:

$$Q \leq Demand + Z(\alpha) \cdot \sigma_{Demand} \quad (3-14)$$

Where Q is the upper limit of the quantity demanded

Demand is the quantity demanded

$Z(\alpha)$ is the Z-statistic for $1-\alpha$ probability

σ_{Demand} is the anticipated standard deviation of the Demand

Losses due to overproduction are not necessarily a direct part of a objective function, but are typically implicit in the maximum probability associated with the constraint on product quantity. The maximum probability is defined subjectively, by the owning firm, with a level of acceptance of a Type I error.

The objective function could be revised to account for overproduction losses directly by deducting "the expected loss from disposing of excess production at a lower price" [Johnson, 1974]. However, in this expected value of Z, quantity is a nonlinear variable and "must be solved by nonlinear programming methods" [Johnson, 1974].

3.4 Microeconomic Product Type Estimation

Where a product or resource price (cost) description is not directly available, but its microeconomic type can be surmised, an approximate curve for the type may be described by a first order price (cost) function and an associated marginal revenue function. The angle of the price (cost) curve will vary from 0° (perfectly competitive) to -45° (perfect monopoly), with competitive-monopoly having a -15° angle for a price/cost curve and oligopoly having a -30° angle.

The midpoint of the average revenue curve is at the same quantity as the zero price of the marginal revenue curve, and each curve has the same initial product price (Figure 2). The marginal revenue curve therefore has twice the slope of the average revenue curve do to geometry.

Figure 2: Average and Marginal Revenue Curves

Let α designate the average revenue curve angle (in degrees) for a product (or resource).

The price P at a given quantity Q would then be:

$$P = Q \cdot \tan(\alpha) + P_0 \quad (3-15)$$

Where P is the total price at quantity Q

P_0 is the price/cost at zero quantity

α is the angle of the average revenue curve

The maximum quantity that will be utilized will be where the marginal revenue is zero. That is, since the marginal revenue curve is:

$$MR = Q \cdot 2 \tan(\alpha) + P_0 \quad (3-16)$$

Where MR is the marginal revenue at quantity Q

P_0 is the price/cost at zero quantity

α is the angle of the average revenue curve

the maximum quantity (Q_{\max}) is Q when the marginal revenue, MR is zero:

$$MR = 0 = Q_{\max} \cdot 2 \tan(\alpha) + P_0$$

$$Q_{\max} = \frac{-P_0}{2 \tan(\alpha)} \quad (3-17)$$

Where Q_{\max} is the maximum quantity for a non-negative price

P_0 is the price/cost at zero quantity

α is the angle of the average revenue curve

3.5 Fuzzy Logic

All things are certain to a degree; all measurements are accurate to a degree. Fuzzy logic is an analytical tool that acknowledges imprecision.

Most of the phenomena we encounter everyday are imprecise, that is, they carry a certain degree of fuzziness in the description of their nature. This imprecision may be associated with their shape, position, momentum, color, texture, or even the semantics that describe what they are. In many cases the same concept will have different degrees of imprecision in different contexts or times...This kind of imprecision or fuzziness associated with continuous phenomena is common in all fields of study: sociology, physics, biology, finance, marketing, engineering, oceanography, psychology, health management, and so forth.²

² Cox, Earl. *The Fuzzy Systems Handbook*, AP Professional, Cambridge, Massachusetts 1994: page 21.

3.5.1 Motivation and Application

Models of systems and processes are often represented by equations and formulas; these representations are easy to create, but are approximations that are more or less inaccurate.

The actual selling prices of products and the costs of resources are typically functions of quantity. Price and cost are often approximated as constant values, particularly if these values are only needed at specific levels of quantity. If values of price and cost at various levels of quantity are needed, having a certain number of specific values in hand, but not the ones needed for our evaluation, a function using numerical analysis can be created. Unfortunately, a generated function has two important pitfalls: 1) it will be an approximation to the *real* function (if, indeed, there is a true function from which the data came), often grossly exaggerating the true output the further an input datum is from those original data used to generate the function, and 2) the fact that it *is* an *approximation* is typically ignored, the false assumption being that it is the true representation of a real function.

Revisions and enhancements could be attempted, a deeper analysis into the approximation of the function of quantity being made; of course, as Lofti Zadeh suggested, “The closer one looks at a real-world problem, the fuzzier becomes the solution” [Ross, 1995].

For systems with little complexity, hence little uncertainty, closed-form mathematical expressions provide precise descriptions of the systems...the most complex systems where few numerical data exist and where only ambiguous or imprecise information may be available, fuzzy reasoning provides a way to understand system behavior...Fuzzy systems *can* implement crisp inputs and outputs, and in this case produce a nonlinear functional mapping just as do algorithms.³

³ Ross, Timothy. *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, New York, New York, 1995: 2.

All things are viewed as certain or uncertain; uncertain things are either *random* (stochastic) or *imprecise* (fuzzy or vague)[Kosko, 1992, 1993]. Understanding and analyzing the uncertainty in a system depends upon the employment of methods that reveal both the randomness and imprecision inherent in the system (as well as randomness and imprecision in the analysis itself).

Elements of a fuzzy set can take on any one of an infinite number of values within a select range. A fuzzy value describes the degree of membership of an element to a prototypical component. Imprecise variables that constitute a fuzzy set can be described with a membership function. Most often, this is a *normal* function, showing complete membership at the average value (i.e., 1 at the mean) [Ross, 1995].

Zadeh suggested that *set membership* is the key to decision making when faced with uncertainty...For fuzzy sets, uniqueness is sacrificed, but flexibility is gained because the membership function can be adjusted to maximize the utility for a particular application.⁴

For most cases, those for which complete knowledge of a process, system, or variation is not certain, methods that provide unique (invariant) parameter values are surreptitiously accurate; in these circumstances, fuzzy logic can yield truer accuracy.

...The fuzzy set H is the *function* μ_h that carries X into $[0,1]$. Hence, *every* function that maps X onto $[0,1]$ is a fuzzy set...The membership function embodies the mathematical representation of membership in a set... $\mu_m(x) =$ degree to which $x \in A$.⁵ (A is a fuzzy set.)

⁴ Ross, Timothy. *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, New York, New York, 1995: 10,12.

⁵ Ross, Timothy. *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, New York, New York, 1995: 12.

For an entity A, $\mu_m(x)$ (also noted as $m(x)$) is a unitless value that indicates the degree to which x describes A (how much the part describes the whole [Kosko, 1993]).

*Fuzziness describes the ambiguity of an event, whereas randomness describes the uncertainty in the occurrence of the event.*⁶

Randomness implies ‘How likely’ something is while fuzziness implies “How much alike” something is. How near an object say, A, is to object B, is the perpendicular, Euclidean distance between the two [Kosko, 1992]:

$$d(A,B) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k |a_i - b_i|^2} \quad (3-18)$$

$d(A,B)$ is the distance between A and B
 a_i and b_i are the i th of k members of A and B, respectively

The normalized distance between A and B, or how dissimilar A is from B is given by:

$$d_{\text{norm}}(A,B) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \left| \frac{a_i - b_i}{b_i} \right|^2} \quad (3-19)$$

$d_{\text{norm}}(A,B)$ is the normalized distance between A and B
 a_i and b_i are the i th of k members of A and B, respectively
 B is the prototype to which A is compared

For example, say a particular product type is defined as having characteristics of height, width, depth, and weight of 3”, 4”, 8”, and 31 ounces, respectively. A particular product has a height, width, depth, and weight of 3.5”, 3.8”, 7”, and 30 ounces. The overall mismatch between the product and the product type is:

$$\sqrt{\left| \frac{3'' - 3.5''}{3''} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{4'' - 3.8''}{4''} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{8'' - 7''}{8''} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{31 \text{ Oz} - 30 \text{ Oz}}{31 \text{ Oz}} \right|^2} = 0.267$$

That is, the product matches the product type by $(1-0.267)*100\%$ or 78.3%.

⁶ Ross, Timothy. *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, New York, New York, 1995: 13.

An alternative to an analytical function representing price and cost as dependent variables of quantity is to accumulate specific points of relevant data into a simple, piece-wise linear function and use it as a fuzzy variable. Three advantages of using a price or cost as a fuzzy variable are: 1) the variable (function) is always apparent as an approximation, and 2) the variable can be tuned into an accurate representation of the actual function, and 3) complex mathematics is not required, since the method uses a very controllable, procedural approach.

3.5.2 Fuzzy Associative Memory (FAM)

A real system may require several inputs to produce a single output, and at least some of these inputs may not be related to or interactive with each other. If the inputs are fuzzy variables, the total of inputs typically need not be included in an analysis or prediction of a particular output since fuzzy variables tend to overlap.

...there exists a compact form of representing a fuzzy rule based-system...This compact graphical form is called a fuzzy associative memory table, or FAM table....the rule based system actually represents a general nonlinear mapping from the input space of the fuzzy system to the output space of the fuzzy system.⁷

A system event that transforms, in parallel, the elements of one set of fuzzy variables into another set of fuzzy variables as a series of FAM rules. The FAM rules create a general mapping of one set to another. To transform one fuzzy set into another requires all FAM

⁷ Ross, Timothy. *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, New York, New York, 1995: 279.

rules to activate or “fire” at the same time, providing a procedural equivalent of a mathematical function.

To use FAM rules and their associated transformations in a realistic and reasonable way, the output fuzzy set needs to be quantified into a single value. The simplest way to do this is by determining the center of gravity (COG), or centroidal value of the output fuzzy set manipulated as an aggregate. The relative location, x , and degree of membership, $m(x)$, of each element of the output set is used to calculate the centroid:

$$COG = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_1} x_{i1} \cdot m_{i1}(x) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} x_{i2} \cdot m_{i2}(x) + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} x_{ik} \cdot m_{ik}(x)}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_1} m_{i1}(x) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} m_{i2}(x) + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} m_{ik}(x)} \quad (3-20)$$

Where COG is the center of gravity of combined fuzzy variables
 x_i is the abscissa location of element i for the particular fuzzy set
 $m_i(x)$ is the value or degree of membership of element i at x_i for fuzzy set K

For example, Figure 3 shows two curves describing two individual fuzzy variables for which a single parameter value needs to be determined.

Figure 3: The Center of Gravity for Two Fuzzy Curves

The centroid, cog, of the two curves, using (3-20):

$$\frac{(0 \cdot 5 + 1 \cdot 7 + 2 \cdot 9 + 3 \cdot 9 + 4 \cdot 9 + 5 \cdot 9 + 6 \cdot 6 + 7 \cdot 3 + 8 \cdot 0) + (2 \cdot 0 + 3 \cdot 2 + 4 \cdot 4 + 5 \cdot 6 + 6 \cdot 6 + 7 \cdot 6 + 8 \cdot 6 + 9 \cdot 6 + 10 \cdot 6)}{(5 + 7 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 3 + 0) + (0 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6)} = 4.91$$

The single parameter value is then 4.91.

3.5.3 Fuzzy Microeconomics

A Fuzzy Associative Memory can be used to approximate a product's type. Four fuzzy membership curves, each one a triangular curve spaced in turn along a unit abscissa, depicts Perfect Competition (mean at 0.0), Competitive-Monopoly (mean at 0.25), Oligopoly (mean at 0.75), and Perfect Monopoly (mean at 1.0). A product type, then, ranges from 0, or perfectly competitive, to 1.0, a perfectly monopoly (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Microeconomic Type Membership

The proper shape and location of the fuzzy curves may be tuned to reflect actual evidence, historical data, or real time analysis to reflect the system with increasing fidelity.

Experts can be surveyed as to their opinions on how each of the four product types, mentioned above, match the type of a particular product. For example, on average, expert opinion may deem a particular product to be 10% perfectly competitive, 30% competitive-monopoly, 70% oligopoly, and 90% monopoly. Each product type can individually range from 0% to 100%. If each type happened to be 100%, then the aggregate type would fall precisely in the middle of the unit abscissa, at 0.5.

The percentages can be fine tuned with a “certainty curve” (see Figure 5) that takes into account the inherent non-linearity of human quantification. For example, any belief between 40% to 60% may be roughly equivalent, but 10% could also be very distinct from 20% and 80% from 90%.

Figure 5: Certainty Bias (Fuzzy Hedge)

Expert opinions are applied to the four respective fuzzy membership curves and the centroid is calculated. The assumed product type is the centroidal value or type number (TN) between 0 and 1.

The generated TN is multiplied by the angle of the monopoly (the limiting type) price curve (-45°, the greatest possible price curve angle) to yield the angle, α , of the product's price curve:

$$\alpha = TN * (-45^\circ) \quad (3- 21)$$

The angle of the marginal revenue curve is then $\arctan(2\tan(\alpha))$ (Figure 2).

If the price at zero (or single) quantity is known, the maximum quantity can be determined from the zero crossing of the marginal revenue curve. Quantity dependent prices are determined from the slope of the price curve ($\tan(\alpha)$). For a specific unit change in quantity, the necessary change in price to maintain the slope is unique and readily ascertainable:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta Q} &= \tan(\alpha) \\ \Delta P &= \tan(\alpha) \cdot \Delta Q \\ P_{new} &= P_{old} + \Delta P \end{aligned} \quad (3- 22)$$

Where ΔP is the change in selling price of the product

ΔQ is the change in quantity demanded of the product

P_{old} is the price of the product prior to the change in price of the product

P_{new} is the price of the product after applying the change in price of the product

α is the angle of the price versus quantity curve for the product

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY

A methodology is derived from the basic microeconomic construct of Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution (MRTS) as a pivotal function that relates products to one another into a cohesive system. From the MRTS, a reliable accounting of opportunity cost and marginal profit is obtained. From microeconomic theory and from mathematics, the optimum profit occurs when marginal profit is zero. That is, if zero marginal profit is sought for each product of a manufacturing system, binding the products together with their MRTS, a clean, iterative path toward optimality becomes available.

4.1 Defining the Scope of a Manufacturing System

Manufacturing as a human, social, mechanical, financial, scientific entity is very large in scope. This research narrowly defines manufacturing at the purely financial level. All inputs are resources that have capital value; all outputs are products that also have capital value. The objective, within the narrow financial definition of manufacturing, is to achieve an optimum profit from the products of manufacture in a way that minimizes the advantage of producing one product over another.

Manufacturing can be modeled as a microeconomic system, one that creates a capital market within its defining attributes: the *value of individual resources* that are consumed as a set having value transferred to the *values of products* created to aid the system profit. That is, the manufacturing model is a closed microeconomic system, having available resources and a set of select, attainable products, that is completely defined by *value of the*

resources, the value of consuming the resources, and the value of the products produced and sold.

By modeling manufacturing as a closed system of purely interacting capital value, the actual location of product manufacture is not a necessary consideration. Products that make up the manufacturing system need not be produced at the same physical location. More than one manufacturing facility can be responsible for a single grouping or set of products, just as the source of the resources, that also help make up the manufacturing system, obviously need not be, and most probably cannot be, single and unique. Differences in location of an otherwise identical product or resource create separate and unique manufacturing entities that are described as having unique value that reflect all differences, including locality.

The owning firm establishes the manufacturing system by creating product sets and directing the construction of each member of the set into available physical production units. The production units may be separated by walls, buildings, or oceans. The product set remains a manufacturing entity that is amenable to a closed, microeconomic model. Moreover, microeconomics allows us a clean way of analyzing product sets with members that have diverse origins or other unique aspects. As long as a well-defined capital value can be ascribed to each constituent of the product and resource domains, and major defining characteristics are pre-defined by the owning firm, manufacturing can be modeled as a closed microeconomic system.

Manufacturing is a system of products and resources. Resources have capital costs and these costs vary according to the amount planned for consumption within the system. Products have capital values, or revenue, and these vary according to the amount planned

for sale. Each unit of product has a set of required resources and a requisite quantity for each resource that is needed. Each unit of product, then, has a capital cost.

Having defined manufacturing in terms of revenue and cost, calculations of opportunity cost and marginal profit can be applied to each product and so, too, the subsequent profit of the complete system of products.

When the revenue versus quantity description of a product is not available, or if the data are not current or reliable, fuzzy logic can be used to approximate the description, thus enhancing an otherwise insufficient application of a microeconomic model.

Experts can be surveyed, persons who have a direct knowledge of the product, as to the appropriate microeconomic type. Further surveys can be performed to detect the bias experts may have in the answers given to survey questions and a fuzzy bias variable, that we can apply to the fuzzy microeconomic type variable, can be used to strengthen approximations.

4.2 The FM³ Algorithm

The methodology used for analyzing the microeconomic manufacturing model relies on the marginal profit for each product. The methodology adjusts marginal quantities of products in the direction of nullifying all marginal profits. The methodology provides changing values of all resources and product prices subject to changes in product quantities produced as well as resource quantities consumed.

The methodology allows the following: 1) equilibrium quantities of each product, given defined resource and product domains (including resource and product pricing), 2) equilibrium prices of products, given quantities demanded of products and a defined

resource domain (including resource pricing), 3) resource pricing requirements, given the quantity demanded of products and a defined product domain (including product pricing).

The concept of the methodology is given form in the Fuzzy Microeconomics Model of Manufacturing (FM³) algorithm. The FM³ algorithm contains the following five steps:

- 1) Identify product domain, P, as a set of n elements each with a capital value p(Q)
- 2) Identify resource domain, R, as a set of m elements each with a capital value r(Q)

Define the unit resource cost, UC, for each product as sum of required resources:

$$UC_k = \sum_{i=1}^m q_{k,i} \cdot r_i \quad (4-1)$$

Where $q_{k,i}$ is the quantity of resource i used to manufacture product k

r_i is the value of resource i

UC_k is the unit cost of product k using m resources

Initialize the set of quantities, Q, for each product k.

- 3) Determine Iq_k , the marginal quantity of product k, or the quantity that changes the pricing structure of at least one element of the product or resource domains.

$$Iq_k > 0 \text{ iff } (p_k - UC_k - OC_k) < 0$$

$$Iq_k = 0 \text{ iff } (p_k - UC_k - OC_k) = 0 \quad (4-2)$$

$$Iq_k < 0 \text{ iff } (p_k - UC_k - OC_k) > 0$$

where p_k is the (marginal) revenue generated by Iq_k of product k

UC_k is the total (marginal) cost generated by Iq_k of product k

OC_k is the opportunity cost of failing to use the value of resources in the next best product

Q_k is the total quantity of product k

$$Q_{k_new} = Q_{k_old} + Iq_k \quad (4-3)$$

Where Q_{k_new} is the new quantity for product k

Q_{k_old} is the previous quantity of product k

Iq_k is the incremental quantity

- 4) Is $I_{q_k} = 0$ for all products k ?
 - If not, then repeat step 3)
 - Otherwise continue to 5)
- 5) Show optimum quantities, Q_k

Step 1 in the algorithm requires the product *domain* be selected for evaluation. The product domain consists of one or more members. The resource requirements of each product is determined at step 2.

Step 2 in the algorithm identifies the resource requirements of each product. A *resource domain* is determined by the resource needs of the products.

Step 3 is the iterative step, where marginal changes are made to the quantity of each product. The marginal profits (revenue less costs of resource and opportunity) determine the amount and sign of the marginal changes of the next iteration.

Step 4 is the branch returning or terminating iteration. When the marginal profit is zero for each product, maximum overall profit has been achieved and the iterations cease. When optimality has been achieved, Step 5 is executed. However, Step 5 is also executed if the process becomes degenerate, and the set of quantities of the most profitable iteration is considered the optimal set.

4.3 Examples

The following examples begin by describing a two-product system and the basic general calculations involved in determining opportunity costs and marginal profits. Broad, static

changes are then made to the system and actual calculations are performed. Finally, a realistic system of three products is analyzed in a systematic way.

4.4.1 General Description

Let us say that a product domain consists of two products. The two products have pricing P_1 and P_2 , and production quantities Q_1 and Q_2 . The resource domain contains three resources, R_1, R_2, R_3 . The products have the following resource requirements (unit costs, UC_1 for product #1 and UC_2 for product #2):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Product}_1 &\rightarrow UC_1 = 2*R_1 + R_2 + R_3 \\ \text{Product}_2 &\rightarrow UC_2 = 4*R_1 + R_2 + 2*R_3 \end{aligned}$$

The marginal opportunity costs (equation 3-9) for each product is then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Product}_1 &\rightarrow OC_1 = MRTS_{21}*P_1 - UC_1 = P_2*UC_1/UC_2 - UC_1 \\ \text{Product}_2 &\rightarrow OC_2 = MRTS_{12}*P_2 - UC_2 = P_1*UC_2/UC_1 - UC_2 \end{aligned}$$

The marginal profit (3-10) for each product is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Product}_1 &\rightarrow MP_1 = P_1 - OC_1 - UC_1 \\ &= P_1 - P_2*(UC_1/UC_2) \\ \text{Product}_2 &\rightarrow MP_2 = P_2 - OC_2 - UC_2 \\ &= P_2 - P_1*(UC_1/UC_2) \\ &= P_2*(1 - MRTS_{12}) \end{aligned}$$

Overall profit for a product is given by the quantity produced times the marginal profit without including opportunity costs (i.e., $MP_n + OC_n$) and this is the same as the quantity times the unit selling price less the unit resource costs:

$$\text{Profit}_n = Q_n * (MP_n + OC_n) = Q_n * (P_n - UC_n)$$

The profit (3-11) for each product is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Product}_1 &\rightarrow \text{Profit}_1 = Q_1 * (MP_1 + OC_1) = Q_1 * (P_1 - UC_1) \\ \text{Product}_2 &\rightarrow \text{Profit}_2 = Q_2 * (MP_2 + OC_2) = Q_2 * (P_2 - UC_2) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.2 Example #1: Using Constant Pricing

Assumptions: all resource costs and product prices are constant. Prices of all resources, $R = \{R_1, R_2, R_3\} = \{\$1.75, \$3.50, \$7.00\}$, and for products, $P = \{P_1, P_2\} = \{\$32.00, \$56.00\}$.

The unit resource costs (Marginal resource costs) are:

$$UC_1 = 2 \cdot R_1 + R_2 + R_3 = \$14.00$$

$$UC_2 = 4 \cdot R_1 + R_2 + 2 \cdot R_3 = \$24.50$$

Objective: Given the above assumptions, which product should have priority, and what are the optimum quantities, Q_1 and Q_2 , for products one and two respectively?

The opportunity costs are first calculated:

$$OC_1 = P_2 \cdot UC_1 / UC_2 - UC_1 = \$18.00$$

$$OC_2 = P_1 \cdot UC_2 / UC_1 - UC_2 = \$31.50$$

Marginal profit (MP) is calculated for products 1 and 2

$$\begin{aligned} MP_1 &= P_1 - OC_1 - UC_1 = \$32.00 - \$18.00 - \$14.00 = \$0.00 \\ &= P_1 - P_2 \cdot (UC_1 / UC_2) = \$32.00 - \$56.00 \cdot (0.57143) = \$0.00 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} MP_2 &= P_2 - OC_2 - UC_2 = \$56.00 - \$31.50 - \$24.50 = \$0.00 \\ &= P_2 - P_1 \cdot (UC_2 / UC_1) = \$56.00 - \$32.00 \cdot (1.75) = \$0.00 \end{aligned}$$

The zero values of the marginal profits signify that the manufacture of the two products are in microeconomic equilibrium, that is, *optimized*; since the marginal revenue (which is also the price, P , in this case) is the same as the marginal cost (opportunity plus resource), the marginal profit is zero for both products of the closed microeconomic system.

The two products create a microeconomic system. Moreover, since the resources and the product pricing are constant for any and all quantities, pricing has infinite elasticity (as well as do the costs). In this example, any quantity of either product can be manufactured without affecting the equilibrium of the system. To maximize profit, both products should be made as long as all resources can be maintained and all quantities are sellable.

The system of Example #1 is a trivial one. Any changes to either resource cost or product price will disturb the equilibrium, creating a negative marginal profit for one product, the other product being favored with its positive marginal product. If the system maintains the perfectly competitiveness of its elements, a price change in one product will also cause one of the products to have resource priority over the other.

For example, suppose the cost of resource 3 (R3) doubles to \$14.00 per unit, then the marginal profits are:

$$\begin{aligned} MP_1 &= \$1.45 \\ MP_2 &= -\$2.67 \end{aligned}$$

These marginal profits indicate that all available resources are better applied to product #1.

If manufacturing does continue producing both products with resource three at \$14.00, then there has been a tacit determination by the owning firm to subsidize the manufacture of product #2; and this subsidy is negative of the marginal profit (MP_2).

If the owning firm were able to adjust the price of the two products, it could increase the price of product #2 by \$2.67 or decrease the price of product #1 by \$1.45, depending upon particular marketing strategies (or other reasons not directly related to product manufacture). Table 1 shows the product prices that yield equilibrium (within \$0.01) when the cost of resource three is doubled to \$14.00:

Table 1: Equilibrium From Subsidies

Product 1 Price (Subsidy)	Product 2 Price (Subsidy)
\$32.73 (\$0.73)	\$60.00 (\$4.00)
\$32.00 (\$0.00)	\$58.67 (\$2.67)
\$31.50 (-\$0.50)	\$57.75 (\$1.75)

\$31.00 (-\$1.00)	\$56.83 (\$0.83)
-------------------	------------------

These prices (subsidies) are a selection of the set of subsidies possible that maintain microeconomic equilibrium. Of course, since both products are perfectly competitive (our original assumption), the selling price cannot change and the firm would have to pay the subsidy itself (by manufacturing both products for the initial selling price).

4.4.3 Example #2: Using Block Pricing

The description of Example 1 is modified as follows: product #2 has the block pricing shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Block Pricing for Product #2

Quantity	Price of Product #2 @ Stated Quantity
< 100	\$100.00
100 to 1,000	\$80.00
1,000 to 10,000	\$60.00
Over 10,000	\$50.00

Table 3 shows the marginal profits of the two products, using Table 2's block pricing on product #2.

Table 3: Marginal Profits using the Block Pricing of Product #2

Product #2 Quantity Built	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
<100	\$32.00	\$100.00	-\$25.14	\$44.00
100 to <1K	\$32.00	\$80.00	-\$13.71	\$24.00
1K to 10K	\$32.00	\$60.00	-\$2.29	\$4.00
>10K	\$32.00	\$50.00	\$3.43	-\$6.00

The marginal profits indicate that product #2 should be manufactured when its quantity requirements are not greater than 10,000 units; product #1 has preference when product #2 quantities exceed 10,000 units. Moreover, if quantities in excess of 10,000 units are required, other facilities, where resources may be cheaper, should be considered for the manufacture of product #2. (Note: even when manufactured at another location, the manufacturing system still maintains the product in the same qualitative way as part of a

closed microeconomic system; only the *value* of the unit costs, resource allocation, product interrelationship is modified.)

Suppose both products are subject to the block pricing of Table 4.

Table 4: Block Pricing used for Both Products

Quantity Built	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
<100	\$50.00	\$100.00	-\$7.14	\$12.50
100 to <1K	\$40.00	\$80.00	-\$5.71	\$10.00
1K to 10K	\$35.00	\$60.00	\$0.71	-\$1.25
>10K	\$30.00	\$50.00	\$1.43	-\$2.50

The marginal profits (MP1 and MP2) indicate that product #2 has preference when quantities for both products are below 1000 units; product #1 has preference when quantities for both products are 1000 units or greater. Table 4 gives us no useful information when one product is in a different block from the other (e.g., product #1 quantity is < 100 and product #2 quantity is 1K to 10K); this information is shown in Tables 5 through 8.

Table 5: Marginal Profits with Q1 < 100

Quantity product #1	Quantity product #2	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
<100	<100	\$50.00	\$100.00	-\$7.14	\$12.50
<100	100 to <1K	\$50.00	\$80.00	\$4.29	-\$7.50
<100	1K to 10K	\$50.00	\$60.00	\$15.71	-\$27.50
<100	>10K	\$50.00	\$50.00	\$21.43	-\$37.50

When product #1 quantities are less than 100 units (Table 5), product #2 should have preference as long as the quantity demanded for product #2 is also less than 100 units.

Table 6: Marginal Profits with $100 \leq Q1 < 1000$

Quantity product #1	Quantity product #2	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
100 to <1K	<100	\$40.00	\$100.00	-\$17.14	\$30.00
100 to <1K	100 to <1K	\$40.00	\$80.00	-\$5.71	\$10.00
100 to <1K	1K to 10K	\$40.00	\$60.00	-\$5.71	\$10.00
100 to <1K	>10K	\$40.00	\$50.00	\$11.43	-\$20.00

Table 7: Marginal Profits with $1000 \leq Q1 < 10,000$

Quantity product #1	Quantity product #2	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
1K to 10K	<100	\$35.00	\$100.00	-\$22.14	\$38.75
1K to 10K	100 to <1K	\$35.00	\$80.00	-\$10.71	\$18.75
1K to 10K	1K to 10K	\$35.00	\$60.00	\$0.71	-\$1.25
1K to 10K	>10K	\$35.00	\$50.00	\$6.43	-\$11.25

Table 8: Marginal Profits with $Q1 > 10,000$

Quantity product #1	Quantity product #2	Price (#1) @ Stated Quantity	Price (#2) @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
>10K	<100	\$30.00	\$100.00	-\$27.14	\$47.50
>10K	100 to <1K	\$30.00	\$80.00	-\$15.71	\$27.50
>10K	1K to 10K	\$30.00	\$60.00	-\$4.50	\$7.50
>10K	>10K	\$30.00	\$50.00	\$1.43	-\$2.50

When product #1 quantities are 100 to 1,000 units (Table 6), product #1 should have preference as long as the quantity demanded for product #2 is not greater than 10,000 units. When product #1 quantities are 1,000 to 10,000 units (Table 7), product #1 should have preference as long as the quantity demanded for product #2 is 1,000 units or more. When product #1 quantities are greater than 10,000 units (Table 8), product #1 should have preference only when the quantity demanded for product #2 is also greater than 10,000 units.

Now let us suppose that both products have the original pricing of Example #1 but the three resources have the block pricing shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Marginal Profits with Resource Block Pricing

Quantity Demanded	R1 Cost @ Stated Quantity	R2 Cost @ Stated Quantity	R3 Cost @ Stated Quantity	MP1	MP2
<100	\$2.50	\$7.00	\$14.00	-\$0.36	\$0.62
100 to <1K	\$2.00	\$5.60	\$11.20	-\$0.36	\$0.62
1K to 10K	\$1.27	\$3.50	\$7.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
>10K	\$1.23	\$2.63	\$5.25	-\$0.08	\$0.14

Here equilibrium is reached when the quantity demanded of product #1 and the quantity demanded of product #2 are between 1000 and 10,000 units; marginal profits are very near equilibrium when the quantities demanded of both products are greater than 10,000 units. If the manufacturer decided to keep equilibrium within \$1.00, any of the stated quantities would support microeconomic equilibrium.

4.4.4 Example #3: Automated Analysis

In this example a tableau technique is used to help automate equilibrium calculations. The system is one with a Resource Domain consisting of three resources (R1, R2, R3), described in Figure 2:

The unit costs for the three products are:

$$\begin{aligned} UC_1 &= 2 * R_1 && + R_3 \\ UC_2 &= R_1 + && R_2 \\ UC_3 &= && R_2 + R_3 \end{aligned}$$

Opportunity costs (OC) and marginal profits (MP) are calculated using equations (3-9) and (3-10), respectively.

Assume the owning firm dictates that manufacturing must not exceed 200 units for any of the products. Assume also that the basic unit of quantity is 10 units; the resources are unlimited as far as this system is concerned. As shown by the resources description of Figure 2, the cost of R3 rises for consumption greater than 90 units. The tables below begin with all products at maximum quantities (Table 10); when a product has a positive

or zero marginal profit at *maximum* quantity, that product's column is highlighted, designating that it is no longer (if ever) valid to use it to calculate the opportunity costs of the other products, though its own opportunity cost *is* calculated.

Table 10: Initial Table

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	200	200	200	600	400	400
Unit Price	5.00	10.00	2.50	1.00	1.00	3.00
UC	$2*1+0+3=5.00$	$1+0+1=2.00$	$0+1+3=4.00$			
OC	$10*5/2-5=20.00$	$5*2/5-2=0.00$	$10*4/2-4=16.00$			
MP	$5-5-20=-20.00$	$10-2-0=8.00$	$2.5-4-16=-17.50$			
QUANT	95	200	95			
Total Profit	\$0.00	\$1,600.00	-\$300.00			

The initial table, Table 10, begins with all products set to maximum quantities. For all tables, the resource quantities are calculated from the product quantities and the unit cost (UC) coefficients. The unit prices are derived from the cost (price) versus quantity graphs of Figure 6 and Figure 7. If a product's Marginal Profit (MP) is zero or greater, the preliminary quantity (noted as Prelim Quant) is the quantity (noted as QUANT) of the product for the next table; if the MP is negative, the product with the most negative MP takes the next lowest block quantity in the next table. In the initial table, Table 10, opportunity costs are zero since all products are at their maximum quantities; that is, an alternate product does not exist in this trivial case.

Figure 6: Resource Costs for Example

The Product Domain consists of three products (P1, P2, P3), described below:

Figure 7: Product Pricing for Example

Table 11: Products 1 and 3 Quantities at 90

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	90	200	90	380	290	180
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	5.00	1.00	1.00	2.50
UC	4.50	2.00	3.50			
OC	1.93	1.33	2.33			
MP	1.07	6.67	-0.83			
QUANT	80	200	80			
Total Profit	\$270.00	\$1,600.00	\$135.00			

Only product number 2 (Prod2) has a positive marginal profit and total profit for the system is \$1300.00; the maximum quantity is therefore maintained for Prod2 and decrease the other quantities per the appropriate product or resource block price (in this case, R3) in the next table, Table 11.

In Table 11, only products 1 and 3 use resource number 3, so each is decremented by ten (minimum prescribed decrement). Now, product number 3 has a less negative MP and system profit is \$2005.00.

Table 11 is repeated by decrementing products 1 and 3 once again, as seen in Table 12. In Table 12, all MP's are improved and total profit is \$2040.00.

Table 12: Products 1 and 3 Quantities at 80

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	80	200	80	360	280	160
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	5.00	1.00	1.00	2.00
UC	4.00	2.00	3.00			
OC	2.67	1.75	2.63			
MP	0.83	6.25	-0.63			
QUANT	70	200	70			
Total Profit	\$280.00	\$1,600.00	\$160.00			

Again products number 1 and 3 are decremented, as shown in Table 13. In Table 13, all MP's are improved again and total profit is \$2055.00.

Table 13: Products 1 and 3 Quantities at 70

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	70	200	70	340	270	140
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	5.00	1.00	1.00	1.50
UC	3.50	2.00	2.50			
OC	3.50	2.29	2.86			
MP	0.50	5.71	-0.36			
QUANT	60	200	60			
Total Profit	\$280.00	\$1,600.00	\$175.00			

Products 1 and 3 are again decremented, in Table 14, and the MP for product 1 is substantially worsened; however, the MP for product number 2 is optimal and the MP for product number 3 is over-efficient. Total profit is \$2350.00.

Table 14: Products 1 and 3 Quantities at 60

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	60	200	60	320	260	120
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	10.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
UC	3.00	2.00	2.00			
OC	12.00	8.00	3.00			
MP	-7.50	0.00	5.00			
QUANT	120	200	60			
Total Profit	\$270.00	\$1,600.00	\$480.00			

The previous tables could have been processed by adjusting the quantity of product number 1 down to the maximum of its next block price (120 units at \$7.50 each) and only incrementally adjusting the quantity of product number 3 with regard to the block pricing of resource 3. Having done this, Table 15, below, would become evident, with a total profit of \$2350.00 (the same profit as Table 14 above, but for different quantities). Table 15, however, has a negative MP for product 1 that is potentially easier to incorporate into the selling price of the product (\$5.36 rather than \$7.50).

Table 15: Same Profit as Table 14, Different Quantities

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	120	200	60	440	260	180
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	10.00	1.00	1.00	2.50
UC	4.50	2.00	3.50			
OC	8.36	3.71	2.33			
MP	-g6	4.29	4.17			
QUANT	10	200	90			
Total Profit	\$360.00	\$1,600.00	\$390.00			

Table 16, derived from Table 14, increases the price of product number 1 from \$7.50 to \$12.86, bringing products 1 and 3 into equilibrium; product number one is at maximum selling capacity, so its over-efficiency is not a concern. Total profit is \$2993.20 for this table.

Table 16: Derived from Table 14, Forcing Equilibrium

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	120	200	60	440	260	180
Unit Price	12.86	10.00	10.00	1.00	1.00	2.50
UC	4.50	2.00	3.50			
OC	8.36	3.71	6.50			
MP	0.00	4.29	-0.00			
QUANT	10	200	90			
Total Profit	\$1002.86	\$1,600.00	\$390.00			

As an alternate solution, Table 17 is derived from Table 14. As in Table 16 above, a new unit selling price for product number 1 is derived by subtracting the MP for Prod1 (-\$7.50) from the current selling price of \$7.50, yielding a proposed \$15.00 selling price. This proposed price puts the entire system of three products into microeconomic equilibrium with a total profit of \$2800.00.

Table 17: Derived from Table 14, Forcing Complete Equilibrium

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
--	-------	-------	-------	----	----	----

Prelim Quant	60	200	60	320	260	120
Unit Price	15.00	10.00	10.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
UC	3.00	2.00	2.00			
OC	12.00	8.00	8.00			
MP	0.00	0.00	0.00			
QUANT	120	200	60			
Total Profit	\$720.00	\$1,600.00	\$480.00			

The proposed price change of Table 16 is potentially superior to that of Table 17 for two reasons: 1) it would increase system profit by \$193.20, and, perhaps more importantly, 2) a selling price of \$12.86 is more feasible than one of \$15.00. The fact that Table 17 maintains the system of products in equilibrium, including product 2 (something that the competing table, Table 16, does not provide) is of little practical relevance because product 2 is at maximum sellable capacity with a positive marginal profit in the competing table-- it does not effectively *undermine* the system profit, though it might if our sellable assumption were not correct.

Table 18, derived from Table 16, essentially achieves equilibrium for products 1 and 3 when the price of R1 is only \$0.07, yielding a total profit of \$2759.20.

Table 18: With Resource 1 Cost at \$0.07

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	120	200	60	440	260	180
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	10.00	0.07	1.00	2.50
UC	2.64	1.07	3.50			
OC	4.90	1.99	6.44			
MP	-0.04	6.94	0.06			
QUANT	10	200	90			
Total Profit	\$583.20	\$1,786.00	\$390.00			

Table 19, derived from Table 17, achieves equilibrium for products numbers 1 and 3 when the price of R1 is adjusted to \$0.25, yielding a total profit is \$2590.00.

Table 19: With Resource 1 Cost at \$0.25

	Prod1	Prod2	Prod3	R1	R2	R3
Prelim Quant	60	200	60	320	260	120
Unit Price	7.50	10.00	10.00	0.25	1.00	1.00
UC	1.50	1.25	2.00			
OC	6.00	5.00	8.00			
MP	0.00	3.75	0.00			
QUANT	20	200	80			
Total Profit	\$360.00	\$1,750.00	\$480.00			

Although Table 18 yields a larger profit than Table 19, the change in cost from \$1.00 to \$0.25 is more realizable than a change to \$0.07. Perhaps surprisingly, using the product quantities of Table 14, rather than those of Table 16, may be more realistic for the evaluation and recommendation of resource costs.

4.4.5 Example #4: Fuzzy Product Typing

In this example, software utility (presented in Chapter 5) is used that implements the FM³ algorithm (see Appendix G). This example is based on the same manufacturing system analyzed in the Validation Study of Chapter 6, except that here, surveys are used from six experts (engineers and managers who have some familiarity with the products) to determine the product types in lieu of a specified pricing structure. The actual pricing structure of Appendix E is used in the Validation Study, since it actually portrays the products' value to the manufacturing system. In the example here, the use and caveats of employing fuzzy types are demonstrated when a definite structure is absent.

Figure 8 shows the contents of the file used by the software utility (FM3.EXE) that describes the four basic product types (lines starting with C, B, O, M, for competitive,

competitive-monopoly, oligopoly, monopoly) and a description of certainty bias (line starting with S).

```

;Microeconomic fuzzy types
;competitive
C 3 0 1 0.25 0 1 0
;competitive-monopoly
B 3 0 0 0.25 1 1 0
;oligopoly
O 3 0 0 0.75 1 1 0
;monopoly
M 3 0 0 0 0.75 1 1.0
;certainty
S 10 0 0.018 .125 .153 .25 .201 .375 .408 .5 .495 .625 .594 .75 .709 .875
.793 1 .939 1000000 1
@

```

Figure 8: Input File for Microeconomic Types and Certainty Bias

The descriptions are in the form of position/membership points that define fuzzy membership curves. The *certainty* curve is derived from survey data (Appendix C) and is used to normalize human bias from product surveys (Appendix B). Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the graphs of product types and certainty, respectively, created from the data of Figure 8.

The four fuzzy product type curves are triangular with maximum membership (of 1.0) on the abscissa at 0.0 for the competitive type, 1.0 for the monopoly type, and 0.25 and 0.75 respectively for the competitive-monopoly and oligopoly types.

The certainty surveys of Appendix C were completed by the same experts who completed the product type surveys of Appendix B. A specified percentage directly translates to a *certainty* percentage, and this certainty percentage is used to *fix* or normalize the expert information. The process of *fixing* fuzzy data in such a way is known as applying a *fuzzy hedge*.

Figure 9 contains the input file text for FM3.DAT and consists of three sections. The first section describes five products, P0F through P4F (the F designates a fuzzy product type description); these are line commands to the utility program that contains an initial (zero quantity) product price followed by various degrees of the four product types in sequence: competition, competitive-monopoly, oligopoly, monopoly.

```

;Fuzzy Logic Example
;Product Domain: 5 Coilcraft Filters

;Fuzzy price descriptions
;P  Po  COMP  COM-MON  OLIG  MONO
P0F 14.5 29.17 74.17 43.33 0.83
P1F 15 29.17 71.67 46.67 0.83
P2F 15 14.17 66.67 55.83 16.67
P3F 17.5 27.5 51.67 50 34.17
P4F 18 29.17 68.33 50 8.33

;resource cost descriptions
R0 11 0 .079 52.04 .079 71.26 .079 76.43 .081 100.8 .081 103.43 .076
    121.62 .073 144.46 .081 155.81 .081 201.15 .076 1000000 .076
R1 11 0 .045 52.04 .045 71.26 .045 76.43 .051 100.8 .051 103.43 .045
    121.62 .040 144.46 .048 155.81 .048 201.15 .045 1000000 .045
R2 11 0 .109 50.41 .109 71.08 .108 88.76 .108 102.73 .108 136.96 .099
    163.1 .098 203.24 .099 249.19 .107 251.67 .107 1000000 .107
R3 6 0 .017 200 .017 1000 .017 2000 .017 4000 .011 1000000 .011
R4 5 0 .04 200 .04 1000 .034 2000 .023 1000000 .023
R5 7 0 .169 1 .169 9 .169 10 .158 99 .158 100 .141 1000000 .141
R6 7 0 .475 1 .475 9 .475 10 .446 99 .446 100 .407 1000000 .407
R7 7 0 1.322 1 1.32 9 1.32 10 1.24 99 1.24 100 1.13 1000000 1.13
R8 7 0 2.28 1 2.28 9 2.28 10 2.14 99 2.14 100 1.96 1000000 1.96
R9 1 0 6.361

;unit cost descriptions for each product
U0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U2 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U3 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1
U4 0 0 2 0 1 0 1 0 1 1.156

;F to force equilibrium via price
F
@

```

Figure 9: Input Data File for Fuzzy Example

The initial product prices are drawn from the single product prices in the Product Price Structure table of Appendix E.

The second section describes ten resources (R0 through R9) that comprise the resource domain, each line command containing a list of (quantity, cost) points. The third section

lists the unit costs of each product (U0 through U4, corresponding to P0 through P4) as coefficients to the resources, R0 through R4.

Two iterative searches are run, using the software utility and the aforementioned input files. The first search sets the product quantities to values exceeding those for which the marginal revenue would be zero, according to equation (3-17) (the utility auto sizes the initial quantities according to specified or calculated maximum values). The iterative search is run a second time, setting all product quantities to zero. In this way, convergence is expected at one or two (local) optimal product quantity sets from each end of the quantity limits. The best local optimum set is chosen as the solution.

The software utility will *force* equilibrium on the optimal solution tableau (actually the utility will force equilibrium *all* tableaus) by applying the marginal profits to the selling price of the products. Each *forced equilibrium* tableau is created in addition to each normal tableau, as an alternate to each normal tableau and for each iteration of the FM³ algorithm.

Figure 10 shows part of an output file generated by the software utility for the first iterative search run. The output file, FM3.DIA, is a diagnostics file that tracks both fuzzy product calculations and intermediate tableau calculations. The maximum quantities, MAXQ's, are actually less than 20 units for each product, based on equation (3-17) (Note that (3-16) uses twice the slope, alpha, of the price curve). The actual quantity at \$0 is stated as under 44 units for each product, determined by equation (3-14).

```

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility
Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranic
COMMAND LINE: 10 500 500 500 500 500 1000

FAM->[0] alpha:-20.23° MAXQ:19.68 Q@$0:39.35 TYPE:0.45 PRICE:7.25 QUANT: 19.68
FAM->[1] alpha:-20.23° MAXQ:20.35 Q@$0:40.71 TYPE:0.45 PRICE:7.50 QUANT: 20.35
FAM->[2] alpha:-22.50° MAXQ:18.11 Q@$0:36.21 TYPE:0.50 PRICE:7.50 QUANT: 18.11
FAM->[3] alpha:-22.50° MAXQ:21.12 Q@$0:42.25 TYPE:0.50 PRICE:8.75 QUANT: 21.12
FAM->[4] alpha:-22.50° MAXQ:21.73 Q@$0:43.46 TYPE:0.50 PRICE:9.00 QUANT: 21.73

```

Figure 10: Segment from Output Diagnostics File, FM3.DIA

The initial tableau (Figure 11) is also the optimum tableau, with a quantity set for products P0 (PROD #1) through P4 (PROD #5) as $Q = \{17, 18, 15, 18, 18\}$. This quantity set yields a system profit of \$59.66; the system is also in equilibrium ($\Sigma MP = 0$). Figure 12 shows the tableau when the utility forces equilibrium on the system by adjusting product prices; however, since equilibrium has already been achieved for the prices as they are, the tableau is identical to that of Figure 11.

```

BEST Tableau was #17:

```

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	29	9	19	27	20
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	27	20	27	20	49
COST	\$0.16	\$0.45	\$1.24	\$2.14	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	9	9	9	10	10
PRICE	\$11.30	\$11.55	\$11.23	\$13.31	\$13.97
UC	\$7.82	\$7.85	\$7.85	\$9.07	\$10.20
OC	\$3.66	\$3.67	\$3.67	\$3.35	\$4.77
MP	\$-0.18	\$0.02	\$-0.30	\$0.89	\$-1.00
PROFIT	\$3.48	\$3.70	\$3.37	\$4.24	\$3.77
TOTPRF	\$30.21	\$34.59	\$30.72	\$42.93	\$36.71

```

Total Profit: $175.16
Quantity Increment:1

```

Figure 11: Trial #1, Initial (and Final) Tableau

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility					
Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranig					
COMMAND LINE: 10 500 500 500 500 500 1000					
[TABLEAU #1]					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	60	20	43	58	43
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	58	43	58	43	104
COST	\$0.16	\$0.45	\$1.24	\$2.14	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	20	20	18	21	22
PRICE	\$7.25	\$7.50	\$7.50	\$8.75	\$9.00
UC	\$7.82	\$7.85	\$7.85	\$9.07	\$10.20
OC	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
MP	\$-0.57	\$-0.35	\$-0.35	\$-0.32	\$-1.20
PROFIT	\$-0.57	\$-0.35	\$-0.35	\$-0.32	\$-1.20
TOTPRF	\$-11.23	\$-7.23	\$-6.43	\$-6.68	\$-26.02
Total Profit: \$-57.58					
Quantity Increment: 10					

Figure 12: Trial #1, Optimum Tableau

The second iterative search sets product quantities to zero (Figure 13). Figure 14 shows the optimal tableau, in this case the 15th one, yielding a total profit of 175.21, for product quantities, $Q = \{9, 10, 9, 10, 9\}$. Forcing equilibrium (Figure 15) yields a system profit of \$190.34.

**Figure 13:
Initial**

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility					
Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranig					
COMMAND LINE: 100 0 0 0 0 0 10000					
[TABLEAU #1]					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	0	0	0	0	0
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	0	0	0	0	0
COST	\$0.17	\$0.47	\$1.32	\$2.28	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	0	0	0	0	0
PRICE	\$14.50	\$15.00	\$15.00	\$17.50	\$18.00
UC	\$7.91	\$7.95	\$7.95	\$9.23	\$10.37
OC	\$7.08	\$7.11	\$7.11	\$6.80	\$9.28
MP	\$-0.50	\$-0.06	\$-0.06	\$1.46	\$-1.64
PROFIT	\$6.59	\$7.05	\$7.05	\$8.27	\$7.63
TOTPRF	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Total Profit: \$0.00					
Quantity Increment: 100					

**Trial #2,
Tableau**

**Figure
Trial**

BEST Tableau was #21:

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	29	9	18	28	19
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	28	19	28	19	48
COST	\$0.16	\$0.45	\$1.24	\$2.14	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	9	10	9	10	9
PRICE	\$11.18	\$11.32	\$11.27	\$13.36	\$14.27
UC	\$7.82	\$7.85	\$7.85	\$9.07	\$10.20
OC	\$3.70	\$3.72	\$3.72	\$3.62	\$4.83
MP	\$-0.34	\$-0.26	\$-0.30	\$0.67	\$-0.75
PROFIT	\$3.36	\$3.46	\$3.42	\$4.29	\$4.07
TOTPRF	\$30.26	\$34.60	\$30.75	\$42.92	\$36.67

Total Profit: \$175.21
Quantity Increment: 1

**14:
#2,**

Optimum Tableau

**Figure
Trial**

[BEST TABLEAU #21], forcing equilibrium

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	29	9	18	28	19
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	28	19	28	19	48
COST	\$0.16	\$0.45	\$1.24	\$2.14	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	9	10	9	10	9
PRICE	\$11.52	\$11.57	\$11.57	\$13.36	\$15.02
UC	\$7.82	\$7.85	\$7.85	\$9.07	\$10.20
OC	\$3.70	\$3.72	\$3.72	\$4.29	\$4.83
MP	\$0.00	\$-0.00	\$-0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
PROFIT	\$3.70	\$3.72	\$3.72	\$4.29	\$4.83
TOTPRF	\$33.32	\$37.19	\$33.47	\$42.92	\$43.45

Total Profit: \$190.34
Quantity Increment: 1

**15:
#2,**

Forcing Equilibrium

Comparing the results of both iterative search runs, the best quantity set is $Q = \{9, 10, 9, 10, 9\}$, yielding a profit of \$175.21. Further, the example and resulting tableaus suggest increasing the prices of products P0, P1, P2, and P4 to \$11.52, \$11.57, \$11.57, and

\$15.02, leaving P3 at \$13.36, thus making each product equally valuable to the system profit of \$190.34.

If the fuzzy typing employed in an analysis is accurate, a valid optimal solution is expected. If the accuracy of the fuzzy typing is accepted, this acceptance means 1) the accuracy of the experts surveyed is true, 2) the accuracy of the normalization of survey bias is also true, and 3) that simple linearity of the theoretical microeconomic typing is truly representative of the actual product types.

In section 4.4.5 only the expert opinions of product typing are given for the manufacturing system. The system analyzed is the same one that is used in the Validation Study of Chapter 6, where the product pricing structure is prescribed by the owning firm. It will shortly be evident that the actual pricing structure that is employed is not consistent with the expert opinions of what the structure *should* be. Reasons for this could be that the strategy of the owning firm ignores the true microeconomic typing of the particular products, the experts are in error, or a combination of both.

CHAPTER 5 IMPLEMENTATION OF METHODOLOGY

5.1 Requirements of the Implementation

The implementation of the methodology entails the actualization of the FM³ algorithm into software. The implementation is modular, allows piece-wise linear descriptions of products and resources, and provides the facility for approximating product descriptions from theoretical microeconomic types.

5.2 The Algorithm

The algorithm for the methodology has three primary sub-parts: 1) initialization of the global parameters (Figure 16 and Figure 19), 2) limit checking on predefined and revised product quantities (Figure 19), and 3) trial examinations of changes to the quantity structure of the system of products (Figure 18). The main body of the algorithm is shown in Figure 17.

The initialization of global parameters, called simply INITIALIZATION in the program prototype, reads into the program existing data concerning the price versus quantity description of the resource and product domains. Microeconomic type data for creating product descriptions in lieu of product data is also read into the program.

Limit checking, performed by the procedure LIMIT CHECKING, adjusts product and resource quantities if there were limits specified on these quantities. The adjustments are made on products directly according to any specified product limitations. The resources

are adjusted by adjusting the product quantities with regard to minimizing the effect on system profit.

Figure 16: Input Data for FM3.EXE

```

PROGRAM PROTOTYPE: FM3
BEGIN
  CALL INITIALIZATION
  CALL LIMIT CHECKING
  Standard Quantity Change = [predetermined value, e.g., 10]
  Best Profit = 0
  Best Set Of Quantities = Null Set
  Best Trial Profit = Zero
  Best Set Of Trial Quantities = Null Set
  Current Product Quantities = Start Set
  REPEAT
    Delta-Q = Standard Quantity Change
    COUNT = First Product - 1
    WHILE (COUNT ≤ Last Product)
      Increment COUNT
      CALL DELTA-Q TRIAL
    Delta-Q = -Standard Quantity Change
    COUNT = First Product - 1
    WHILE (COUNT ≤ Last Product)
      Increment COUNT
      CALL DELTA-Q TRIAL
    IF Σ(Marginal Profits) <> 0 for the Best Set OF Quantities
      GOTO REPEAT
    Report Best Profit and Best Set Of Quantities
  END

```

Figure 17: Pseudo Code for Main Routine of Utility

```

DELTA-Q TRIAL
  Increase Quantity of Product #COUNT by Delta-Q
  CALL LIMIT CHECKING
  Find the Most Profitable Product (MPP)
  Find the Next Most Profitable Product (NMPP)
  Calculate Opportunity Cost for Each Product, using MPP and NMPP
  Calculate the Marginal Cost of Each Product, Including Opportunity Cost
  Calculate the Marginal Profit of Each Product
  Calculate System Profit from all Marginal Profits
  IF System Profit > Best Profit
    Best Profit = System Profit
    Best Set of Quantities = Current Set
  Restore Current Set of Product Quantities to the Start Set
RETURN

```

Figure 18: Delta Q Trial Routine

```

INITIALIZATION
  READ Description of Resources and Products, including any limits
  READ Microeconomic Type Description
  Determine the Number of Resources (NR) and Products (NP)
  Set Initial Quantities of Products
RETURN

LIMIT CHECKING
  If the Product Quantities are NOT Within Limits
    Adjust Product Quantities
  Set Quantities of Resources Based on Product Quantities
  If the Resource Quantities are NOT Within Limits
    Adjust Product Quantities
  CALL LIMIT CHECKING
RETURN

```

Figure 19: Initialization and Limit Checking Routines

The trial examinations are performed by the procedure DELTA-Q TRIAL. DELTA-Q TRIAL determines the most and next most profitable products, disregarding opportunity costs, for use in calculating the opportunity costs of each product. The opportunity cost of the most profitable product is in regard to the next most profitable product; all other products use the most profitable product for calculations of opportunity cost.

Having calculated the opportunity cost, DELTA-Q TRIAL calculates the marginal profit of each product. DELTA-Q TRIAL calculates total system profit for the current set of product quantities from the marginal profits.

The main body of the algorithm repeats the system profit calculations for individual product quantity changes. Since the system is evaluated once for a decrease in quantity and once for an increase in quantity for each product, the total number of evaluations is twice the number of products.

Ideally, the system will converge to a product quantity set that yields zero marginal profit for all products. Actually, the completed program must check for degeneracy and other problems related to the forced dynamics of the program, and the program may yield final, best quantities for which all marginal profits are not zero, but are minimized.

5.3 The Software Modules

The software is coded in the C++ programming language. The following are the classes and module prototypes that implement the specific aspects of the FM³ algorithm. The main function is also included to show the program flow. Please see Appendix A for the complete software listing and definition of variables.

There are three modules: 1) the main module, FM3.CPP, 2) the module that defines the manufacturing functions, MANUF.CPP and 3) the module that supports the fuzzy logic and Fuzzy Associative Memory processes, FAM.CPP.

5.3.1 MANUF Module

The *element* structure (Figure 20) is used as a point description for finite element curves of price and cost (value) versus quantity.

```
typedef struct element {  
    double quant;  
    double val;  
};
```

Figure 20: The element Structure

The *massType* structure (Figure 21) is used to return the Σ mass of a function (as mass) and the $\Sigma[x*\text{mass}]$ of a function (as xmass); this is primarily useful when finding the centroid of several fuzzy variables that provide a single output.

```
typedef struct massType {  
    double mass;  
    double xmass;  
};
```

Figure 21: The massType Structure

The *manufactureType* class (Figure 22) is used to identify and control a product/resource. The product/resource has an array of elements describing its price versus quantity characteristic.

```

class manufactureType {
    element *m;
    int lastM;
    double Quantity;
    double maxQ;
    double minQ;
    double maxVal;
    int norm;

public:
    //constructors
    manufactureType(int normalize = 0);
    manufactureType(element *memberArray, int normalize = 0);
    //destructor
    ~manufactureType(void);
    void reset(element *memberArray);
    //returns value of membership at quantity
    double getMembership(double quant);
    //sets Quantity to Q
    int setQuantity(double Q) {Quantity = Q; return 0;};
    //get next block quantity before quant
    int getQuantPrior(double quant);
    //get next block quantity after quant int
    int getQuantNext(double quant);
    //return maximum quantity
    double getMaxQ(void) {return maxQ;};
    //return minimum quantity
    double getMinQ(void) {return minQ;};
    //return mass and xmass (x*mass)
    massType calcMass(double memberVal);
    element getNextQ(double quant);
    element getNextVal(double val);
    element getPriorQ(double quant);
    element getPriorVal(double val);
    element getM(int i);
    void list(void);
};

```

Figure 22: The C++ Class manufactureType

Figure 23 contains the function prototype descriptions of the module that performs the primary fuzzy associative memory (FAM) processes. Most of the module is dedicated to setting up the fuzzy variables and associations. The cog() function calculates the centroid of the varying membership product types for a particular product.

```

#define MAXPOINTS 20
#define MAXELEMENTS 10
#define MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS 20

//copies product type curves into a contiguous array
void setupProductTypes(void);

//lists product descriptions
void showProdTypes(void);

//calculates the center of gravity (product type fraction between
//perfect competition (0.0) to perfect monopoly (1.00)
double cog(int ID);

//assigns membership values to each microeconomic type for
product/resource
// with index ID
void assignProdDesc(int ID, double C, double CM, double O, double M);

//routine to read a file containing microeconomic type descriptions
int readTypes(char *dataFileName);

```

Figure 23: The Header File for the Fuzzy Associative Memory (FAM) Module

CHAPTER 6

VALIDATION STUDY

Coilcraft, Inc, located in Northern Illinois, is a manufacturer of magnetic components for the electronics industries. Among the various components Coilcraft builds are filters that aid in eliminating the electrical noise of electronic equipment. A set of related filters is now considered that are relatively new. The product set comprises five filter products, P0, P1, P2, P3, P4, and this constitutes the product domain of the manufacturing system.

6.1 The Goal

The set of product quantities and/or changes to product prices need to be determined that yields equilibrium to within twenty cents; that is, if the system yields all individual marginal profits greater than $-\$0.20$, Coilcraft will consider the system in suitable equilibrium.

6.2 The System Defined

The manufacturing system has a product domain that consists of five members, P0, P1, P2, P3, P4. The design of each member is similar. The five products are manufactured at one location at present, though the possibility exists for one or more of the products to be built at several other facilities around the world. In a normal production period of one month, Coilcraft expects individual product quantities to be less than 1000 units.

There are ten resources that support the product domain, R0 through R9. The tenth resource, R9, is a *composite* resource in that it contains those members of the resource domain used equally by every member of the product domain.

Data for both the product and resource domains originate from predefined corporate information, block price quotes for products, and from vendor data; historical data is also used to define the block pricing of several resources. The product pricing data, for all five products, is in Appendix E; the resource cost information is in Appendix F.

The product prices are depicted graphically in Figure 24. On close inspection, the pricing of products one and two (P1 and P2) have the identical pricing structure. The resource needs of P1 and P2 are also identical. Essentially, P1 and P2 describe the same product.

Figure 24: Product Pricing

Initially, creating a single product from the two identically defined products seems reasonable, providing a smaller, more expedient model of the manufacturing system. However, Coilcraft, as the owning firm, *has* identified the products as separate and this must be abided as dictum. The owning firm is privy to all of its own information, peculiarities, strategies, histories, and options, and so defines the market for the manufacturing system. The analyst may not altogether share in the decision data. The analyst may not know, for example, that product one can be manufactured at any facility, but because of licensing limitations or governmental requirements of some important customers, product two may only be manufactured at a single, pre-selected location. Product two then would have a more limited degree of resource freedom over product one, thus constituting a separate product.

Figure 25 through Figure 29 depict the costs of the ten members of the resource domain that support the manufacturing system.

Figure 25: Costs for Resources R0, R1, R2

Figure 26: Cost for Resource R3

Figure 27: Cost for Resource R4

Figure 28: Costs for Resources R5, R6, R7, R8

Figure 29: Cost for Composite Resource R9

6.3 Running the Iterative Search

Figure 30 shows the input data file (FM3.DAT) for the manufacturing system used by the software utility, FM3.EXE.⁸

```

;Tableau VALIDATION STUDY
;Product Domain: 5 Coilcraft Filters

;product pricing descriptions FIVE products, P0 through P4
P0 14 0 14.5 9 14.5 10 12 49 12 50 11 99 11 100 10.25 249 10.25 250 8.7 499 8.7
    500 7.9 999 7.9 1000 5.3 1000000 5.3
P1 14 0 15 9 15 10 12.5 49 12.5 50 11.5 99 11.5 100 10.75 249 10.75 250 9.2 499 9.2
    500 8.4 999 8.4 1000 5.8 1000000 5.8
P2 14 0 15 9 15 10 12.5 49 12.5 50 11.5 99 11.5 100 10.75 249 10.75 250 9.2 499 9.2
    500 8.4 999 8.4 1000 5.8 1000000 5.8
P3 14 0 17.5 9 17.5 10 15 49 15 50 13.5 99 13.5 100 12.30 249 12.30 250 10.5 499 10.5
    500 9.5 999 9.5 1000 8.95 1000000 8.95
P4 14 0 18.0 9 18.0 10 15.5 49 15.5 50 14.0 99 14.0 100 12.80 249 12.80 250 11.0 499 11.0
    500 9.45 999 9.45 1000 9.45 1000000 9.45

;resource cost descriptions TEN resources, R0 through R9
R0 11 0 .079 52.04 .079 71.26 .079 76.43 .081 100.8 .081 103.43 .076 121.62 .073 144.46
    .081 155.81 .081 201.15 .076 1000000 .076
R1 11 0 .045 52.04 .045 71.26 .045 76.43 .051 100.8 .051 103.43 .045 121.62 .040 144.46
    .048 155.81 .048 201.15 .045 1000000 .045
R2 11 0 .109 50.41 .109 71.08 .108 88.76 .108 102.73 .108 136.96 .099 163.1 .098 203.24
    .099 249.19 .107 251.67 .107 1000000 .107
R3 6 0 .017 200 .017 1000 .017 2000 .017 4000 .011 1000000 .011
R4 5 0 .04 200 .04 1000 .034 2000 .023 1000000 .023
R5 7 0 .169 1 .169 9 .169 10 .158 99 .158 100 .141 1000000 .141
R6 7 0 .475 1 .475 9 .475 10 .446 99 .446 100 .407 1000000 .407
R7 7 0 1.322 1 1.32 9 1.32 10 1.24 99 1.24 100 1.13 1000000 1.13
R8 7 0 2.28 1 2.28 9 2.28 10 2.14 99 2.14 100 1.96 1000000 1.96
R9 1 0 6.361

;unit cost descriptions for each product
U0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U2 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
U3 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1
U4 0 0 2 0 1 0 1 0 1 1.156

;maximum product quantities
< 1000 1000 1000 1000 1000

;F to force equilibrium via price
F
@

```

Figure 30: The Primary Input Data File, FM3.DAT, for the System

⁸ The resource and product information are incorporated into the input files of the software utility included in this research. Please refer to Appendix G for the description of the software related to the input files.

An iterative search is performed in a way that reveals all local optimal quantity sets between the null set (all product quantities set to zero) and a quantity set exceeding expected high values. The software utility, FM3.EXE, increases or decreases product quantities automatically as it strives to zero marginal profits of the product domain, so an intermediate iterative search trial can be performed, setting product quantities to a median value, in addition to trials with zero and extreme quantity sets.

The format of the command line (Figure 31, Figure 34, and Figure 37) begins with the initial setting of ΔQ , the basic change of quantity in an iteration. The next several command line arguments set the initial product quantities. The final command line argument designates the maximum number of iterations for the iterative search run.

```

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility
Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranig
COMMAND LINE: 100 0 0 0 0 0 10000

[TABLEAU #1]

RESC  #1      #2      #3      #4      #5
QUANT  0        0        0        0        0
COST  $0.08    $0.04    $0.11    $0.02    $0.04

RESC  #6      #7      #8      #9     #10
QUANT  0        0        0        0        0
COST  $0.17    $0.47    $1.32    $2.28    $6.36

PROD  #1      #2      #3      #4      #5
QUANT  0        0        0        0        0
PRICE $14.50    $15.00    $15.00    $17.50    $18.00
UC    $7.91    $7.95    $7.95    $9.23    $10.37
OC    $0.00    $0.00    $0.00    $0.00    $0.00
MP    $6.59    $7.05    $7.05    $8.27    $7.63
PROFIT $6.59    $7.05    $7.05    $8.27    $7.63
TOTPRF $0.00    $0.00    $0.00    $0.00    $0.00

Total Profit: $0.00
Quantity Increment: 100

```

Figure 31: Trial #1, Initial Tableau

BEST Tableau was #296:

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	600	99	198	499	299
COST	\$0.08	\$0.05	\$0.10	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	499	299	499	299	813
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	99	200	200	200	99
PRICE	\$11.00	\$10.75	\$10.75	\$12.30	\$14.00
UC	\$7.70	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.96
OC	\$3.13	\$3.14	\$3.14	\$3.59	\$3.89
MP	\$0.17	\$-0.11	\$-0.11	\$-0.13	\$0.15
PROFIT	\$3.30	\$3.03	\$3.03	\$3.46	\$4.04
TOTPRF	\$326.70	\$605.00	\$605.00	\$691.35	\$400.23

Total Profit: \$2628.27
Quantity Increment: 1

Figure 32: Trial #1, Optimum Tableau

[BEST TABLEAU #296], forcing equilibrium

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	600	99	198	499	299
COST	\$0.08	\$0.05	\$0.10	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	499	299	499	299	813
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	99	200	200	200	99
PRICE	\$11.00	\$10.86	\$10.86	\$12.43	\$14.00
UC	\$7.70	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.96
OC	\$3.13	\$3.14	\$3.14	\$3.59	\$4.04
MP	\$0.17	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.00
PROFIT	\$3.30	\$3.14	\$3.14	\$3.59	\$4.04
TOTPRF	\$326.70	\$627.27	\$627.27	\$718.08	\$400.23

Total Profit: \$2699.55
Quantity Increment: 1

Figure 33: #1, Optimum, Forced Equilibrium

The first iterative search trial sets product quantities, $Q = \{Q_0, Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4\}$, to $\{0, 0, 0, 0, 0\}$ (Figure 31). The second iterative search trial initially sets $Q = \{500, 500, 500, 500, 500\}$, a medium quantity set (Figure 34). The third iterative search trial begins with $Q = \{999, 999, 999, 999, 999\}$ (Figure 38), noting the owning firm's limit of less than 1000 units.

```

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility
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COMMAND LINE: 100 500 500 500 500 500 10000

[TABLEAU #1]

RESC  #1      #2      #3      #4      #5
QUANT 1500    500    1000   1500   1000
COST  $0.08    $0.04  $0.11  $0.02  $0.03

RESC  #6      #7      #8      #9     #10
QUANT 1500    1000   1500   1000   2578
COST  $0.14    $0.41  $1.13  $1.96  $6.36

PROD  #1      #2      #3      #4      #5
QUANT 500     500     500     500     500
PRICE $7.90    $8.40  $8.40  $9.50  $9.45
UC    $7.69    $7.72  $7.72  $8.84  $9.97
OC    $0.67    $0.68  $0.68  $0.77  $0.87
MP    $-0.47  $0.00  $0.00  $-0.11 $-1.39
PROFIT $0.21    $0.68  $0.68  $0.66  $-0.52
TOTPRF $103.00  $337.50 $337.50 $331.00 $-259.16

Total Profit: $849.84
Quantity Increment: 100

```

Figure 34: Trial #2, Initial Tableau

Each iterative search trial is executed for a maximum of 10,000 iterations, as noted in the command line.

The first iterative search trial begins with Figure 32, all quantities set to zero. Figure 33 shows the best tableau (Tableau #296), resulting from the iterative search run. The run converges to a system profit of \$2628.27 and a quantity set of $Q = \{99, 200, 200, 200, 99\}$. The marginal profits are fairly low in magnitude, signifying the near equilibrium condition

of the system at these quantities. Applying the marginal profits to the product prices, as in Figure 33, forces the system into complete equilibrium and a total system profit of \$2699.55.

The second iterative search trial, using an initial medium quantity set of $Q = \{500, 500, 500, 500, 500\}$, is shown in Figure 35, with a beginning system profit of \$849.84.

The best tableau of this iterative search run occurred at #33 with $Q = \{200, 249, 400, 249, 200\}$ and product pricing of $\{\$10.25, \$10.75, \$9.20, \$12.30, \$12.80\}$, yielding a system profit of \$3280.93. System equilibrium is not entirely achieved, however, with marginal profits of the first, third, and fifth product at $-\$0.45, -\$1.55,$ and $-\$1.07$ respectively.

When forcing equilibrium (Figure 36), the system yields a profit of \$4205.53 for product pricing of $\{\$10.70, \$10.75, \$10.75, \$12.30, \$13.87\}$.

BEST Tableau was #33:					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	898	200	400	849	449
COST	\$0.08	\$0.05	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	849	449	849	449	1329
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	200	249	400	249	200
PRICE	\$10.25	\$10.75	\$9.20	\$12.30	\$12.80
UC	\$7.69	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.97
OC	\$3.01	\$3.02	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.90
MP	\$-0.45	\$0.00	\$-1.55	\$-0.00	\$-1.07
PROFIT	\$2.56	\$3.03	\$1.47	\$3.46	\$2.83
TOTPRF	\$511.18	\$753.23	\$590.00	\$861.01	\$565.51
Total Profit: \$3280.93					
Quantity Increment: 1					

Figure 35: Trial #2, Optimum

Figure 36: Trial #2, Optimum, Forcing Equilibrium

[BEST TABLEAU #33], forcing equilibrium					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	898	200	400	849	449
COST	\$0.08	\$0.05	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	849	449	849	449	1329
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	200	249	400	249	200
PRICE	\$10.70	\$10.75	\$10.75	\$12.30	\$13.87
UC	\$7.69	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.97
OC	\$3.01	\$3.02	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.91
MP	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.01
PROFIT	\$3.01	\$3.03	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.90
TOTPRF	\$601.78	\$753.23	\$1208.40	\$862.15	\$779.98
Total Profit: \$4205.53					
Quantity Increment: 1					

The third and final iterative search run begins with Figure 37; all product quantities are set to the maximum expected by the owning firm, $Q = \{999, 999, 999, 999, 999\}$. The initial system profit is \$1728.88. The optimal tableau for this run (Figure 38) is #50, yielding a system profit of \$3690.95 for $Q = \{249, 249, 499, 249, 249\}$ and product prices of $\{\$10.25, \$10.75, \$9.20, \$12.30, \$12.80\}$. The system is not in equilibrium, but forcing equilibrium, as shown in Figure 39, yields a system profit of \$4843.54 for product pricing of $\{\$10.70, \$10.75, \$10.75, \$12.30, \$13.87\}$.

Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility					
Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranig					
COMMAND LINE: 100 999 999 999 999 999 10000					
[TABLEAU #1]					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	2997	999	1998	2997	1998
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.01	\$0.02
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	2997	1998	2997	1998	5151
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	999	999	999	999	999
PRICE	\$7.90	\$8.40	\$8.40	\$9.50	\$9.45
UC	\$7.69	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.83	\$9.96
OC	\$0.68	\$0.68	\$0.68	\$0.78	\$0.87
MP	\$-0.47	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.10	\$-1.38
PROFIT	\$0.21	\$0.68	\$0.68	\$0.67	\$-0.51
TOTPRF	\$208.78	\$677.31	\$677.31	\$672.31	\$-506.83
Total Profit: \$1728.88					
Quantity Increment: 100					

Figure 37: Trial #3, Initial Tableau

BEST Tableau was #50:					
RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	997	249	498	997	498
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	997	498	997	498	1534
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	249	249	499	249	249
PRICE	\$10.25	\$10.75	\$9.20	\$12.30	\$12.80
UC	\$7.69	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.97
OC	\$3.01	\$3.02	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.90
MP	\$-0.45	\$0.00	\$-1.55	\$-0.00	\$-1.07
PROFIT	\$2.56	\$3.03	\$1.47	\$3.46	\$2.83
TOTPRF	\$636.44	\$753.23	\$736.02	\$861.10	\$704.15
Total Profit: \$3690.95					
Quantity Increment: 1					

Figure 38: Trial #3, Optimum Tableau

```
[BEST TABLEAU #50], forcing equilibrium
```

RESC	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	997	249	498	997	498
COST	\$0.08	\$0.04	\$0.11	\$0.02	\$0.04
RESC	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
QUANT	997	498	997	498	1534
COST	\$0.14	\$0.41	\$1.13	\$1.96	\$6.36
PROD	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
QUANT	249	249	499	249	249
PRICE	\$10.70	\$10.75	\$10.75	\$12.30	\$13.87
UC	\$7.69	\$7.72	\$7.72	\$8.84	\$9.97
OC	\$3.01	\$3.02	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.90
MP	\$-0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.00	\$0.00	\$-0.00
PROFIT	\$3.01	\$3.03	\$3.02	\$3.46	\$3.90
TOTPRF	\$749.32	\$753.23	\$1507.70	\$862.12	\$971.18

Total Profit: \$4843.54
Quantity Increment: 1

Figure 39: Trial #3, Optimum, Forcing Equilibrium

6.4 Data Analysis and Recommendations

The current system achieves equilibrium with the current pricing structure for product quantities of $Q = \{99, 200, 200, 200, 99\}$ (Figure 32). System profit for these quantities is \$2628.27.

However, if Coilcraft would accept providing a \$0.45 subsidy on product P0 (PROD #1 in Figure 39), a \$1.55 subsidy on P2 (PROD #3 in Figure 39) and a subsidy of \$1.07 of P4 (PROD #5), total system profit will be \$3690.95 with quantities $Q = \{249, 249, 499, 249, 249\}$. The same subsidies hold for quantities $Q = \{200, 249, 400, 249, 200\}$ though a lower system profit of \$3280.93 (Figure 37).

The analysis supports the recommendation that the owning firm manufacture the product domain for $Q = \{249, 249, 499, 249, 249\}$ and consider increasing product pricing from $\{\$10.25, \$10.75, \$9.20, \$12.30, \$12.80\}$ to $\{\$10.70, \$10.75, \$10.75, \$12.30, \$13.80\}$. If

this is done, system profit will be \$4893.54 (Figure 39) and the system will be in complete microeconomic equilibrium.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Conclusions

Microeconomic modeling of manufacturing and the FM³ algorithm suggest that a manufacturing system can be analyzed without external constraints; the FM³ algorithm is self constraining as it seeks to zero marginal profits.

Microeconomic modeling further implies that manufacturing can be viewed on the basis of the capital value of its attributes. Cost is the entity of a resource; price is the entity of a product; opportunity cost is the entity of the interrelationship between products. Capital value and quantity are the sole required descriptions for analysis.

The methodology shows that the use of fuzzy logic has direct application to microeconomics. The potential use in other social sciences is also implied. Social sciences typically have difficulty with mathematical descriptions of intangible attributes such as social integration, group dynamics, decision making, and so on. Fuzzy logic gives a procedural approach to a hitherto analytical solution to problems and concepts that are basically procedural themselves.

Microeconomic modeling of manufacturing gives us the means to identify the interrelationship between products and a method to make each product equally effective to the overall profit of the manufacturing system.

A methodology was developed in which equilibrium is the target principle. When the three attributes of quantity, price, and cost are manipulated toward zero marginal profit, total profit is maximized and each product is equally valuable to the profit.

The FM³ algorithm actualizes the methodology, transforming it into a usable application. The algorithm uses functions of cost, price, and quantity to develop and implement precise calculations of opportunity cost. Opportunity cost is the effective parameter in identifying inequality between product potentials; it also is the main parameter that allows the marginal profit calculation.

7.2 Recommendations

Several enhancements to the FM³ algorithm would increase the robustness of derivative implementations. One enhancement could be the inclusion of replaceable resources. A resource that behaves like an inferior good could have a normal good replacement at specified costs or when a “change over” price has been reached for the target product. Also, pairs of products that have very similar resource requirements may be used as a single product description where one product may be an inferior good and the other a normal good with a pre-defined substitution price or resource cost.

A further enhancement to an FM³ implementation could be the inclusion of a process to track aggregate block prices. That is, since several consumers could order a product at different quantities, hence at differing block prices, the marginal profit calculation becomes far more complex than presented here. The total quantity demanded from all consumers is still used to gauge resource costs, but the individual block prices, and the individual quantities demanded at those prices, need to be evaluated in the marginal cost calculation to accurately predict microeconomic equilibrium conditions.

Fuzzy logic techniques could be expanded to better control the progress toward equilibrium portion of the algorithm. Neural network techniques could aid in creating a self-learning variation of the algorithm; this would be particularly useful for analyzing systems that have long-term viability. A *neural* algorithm could have an initial learning process and then only require periodic updating to yield a dynamic assessment of the system, and it could propose dynamic adjustments to maintain equilibrium. Also, fuzzy logic could automate initial conditions for successive runs of the algorithm, basing them on the most promising quantity sets of the previous runs.

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APPENDIX A

Source Code Listings

The software utility (FM3.EXE) as well as the following source code listings are contained in the accompanying 3.5" floppy diskette (Microsoft® MS-DOS version 6.2) entitled "Using Microeconomics to Model Manufacturing Systems: Source Code".

FM3.CPP

```
/*
*****
//FM3 Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing simulator
//Steven F. Srebranig 1-8-96

#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <ctype.h>
#include <math.h>
#include "general.hpp"
#include "manuf.hpp"
#include "fam.hpp"

//class to store all product quantities and their resultant total profit
class snapShot {
public:
    double Q[MAXELEMENTS];
    double totProfit;
};

//Flag to single end of program
int stopProgram = NO;
//Flag for single run or iteration run
int singleRun = NO;
//Flag to signal that each tableau should be repeated for forced equilibrium
//i.e., for revising product prices with price-MP for all MP < 0
int forceEquilibrium = NO;
//Flag to note that maximum resources were specified ("M" line in FM3.DAT
int maxResourcesSpecified = NO;

***** VARIABLES *****

//total number of products and resources default to MAXELEMENTS
int NUMPROD = MAXELEMENTS;
int NUMRESC = MAXELEMENTS;

//input data file handle
FILE *df;
```

```

//Diagnostics file handle
FILE *diagf;

//quantity increment/decrement
int deltaQ = 10;

//current quantities for products
double QP[MAXELEMENTS];

//current quantities for resources
double QR[MAXELEMENTS];
//allocate class instance for maximum number of resources
manufactureType *R[MAXELEMENTS];
//allocate class instance for maximum number of products
manufactureType *P[MAXELEMENTS];

//array to contain the cost of each resource
double cost[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the selling price of each product
double price[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the unit cost of each product
double unitCost[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the unit profit from each product
double profit[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the marginal profit from each product
double MP[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the opportunity cost of each product
double OC[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the maximum quantity that can be made for each product
double maxQuant[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the maximum quantity of resource that can be allocated
double maxQuantResc[MAXELEMENTS];
//array to contain the minimum quantity that can be made for each product
double minQuant[MAXELEMENTS];

//bestProfit contains the optimu profit for all tableaus yet generated
double bestProfit = 0.0;
//array that contains the profit from the last three tableaus
double recentProfit[3];
//current profit (most recent tableau calculation)
double systemProfit;
//angle of price/cost curve for fuzzy type descriptions
double alpha;
//fuzzy type from 0 (perfectly competitive) to 1 (perfect monopoly)
double type;

//instance of snapShot to store all trials in an iteration,
//the best (most profitable) is used for the final Tableau
//of the current iteration
snapShot trial[2*MAXELEMENTS+1];

//instance of snapShot, containing the optimum tableau product quantities
//and associated profit
snapShot best;

//tracks the number of the optimum tableau
int bestTableau = 0;

//the index to the product price array, p[], for the most profitable product
//for the current tableau
int mostProfitable;

```

```

//the index to the product price array, p[], for the second most profitable
//product for the current tableau
int nextMostProfitable;

//resource requirments for products
double UC[MAXELEMENTS][MAXELEMENTS];

//array of points (quantity,price) describing the price function for products
element p[MAXELEMENTS][MAXPOINTS];

//flag to note whether product description is fuzzy (YES) or not (NO)
int pIsFuzzy[MAXELEMENTS];

//flag to note whether resource description is fuzzy (YES) or not (NO)
int rIsFuzzy[MAXELEMENTS];

//array of points (quantity,cost) describing the cost function for resources
element r[MAXELEMENTS][MAXPOINTS];

//array of points describing the product type function for resources
element fuzzyDesc[MAXPOINTS][5];

//array of points describing the certainty of something (used with pType)
element certainty[MAXPOINTS];

/***** FUNCTION PROTOTYPES *****/

//calculates the unit cost for product proIndex for the current tableau
double calcUC(int proIndex);
//calculates the opportunity cost for all products for the current tableau
void calcOC(void);
//calculates the marginal profit all products for the current tableau
void calcMP(void);
//calculates the price/cost of resource/product index of array E and quantity
//array Q for the values of the current tableau
double calcCost(manufactureType *E[], double *Q, int index);
//calculates the price/cost of resource/product index as a fuzzy variable
//and Fuzzy Associative Memory using quantity array Q for the values of the
//current tableau
double calcFuzzyCost(double quantity,int index);
//calculates all parameters for the current tableau
//if equilibrium is YES, the tableau is changed for product price adjustments
//to force equilibrium
void calcAll(int equilibrium = NO);
//change the quantity of product/resourceprodIndex of A to quant
void changeQuantity(double *A, int prodIndex, double quant);
//updates resource quantities according to the product quantities of the
//current tableau
void updateResourceQuantities(void);
//determines the most and next most profitable products of the current tableau
void calcProfitables(void);
//determines which products should have quantities decremented; each quantity
//change creates a trial tableau, one of which is determined best
void nextInterateDown(void);
//determines which products should have quantities incremented; each quantity
//change creates a trial tableau, one of which is determined best
void nextInterateUp(void);
//uses trial[index] to create the current tableau
void restoreTrial(int index);
//saves the current product quantities and system profit in trial[index]
void loadTrial(int index);
//uses best[index] to create the current tableau

```

```

void restoreBest(void);
//saves the current product quantities and system profit in best
void loadBest(void);
//prints tableaux to file specified by f (defaults to screen)
void printData(FILE *f = stdout);
//resets all trials
void resetTrials(void);
//read and parse initialization data from file FM3.DAT
int readData(void);
//sets up all resource and product description arrays
void setupR_Ps(void);
//writes the current (tableau #count) trials to FM3.DIA, indicating the best
//profit trial (bestT) with '*'
void printTrials(int count,int bestT);
//initializes program
void initialize(void);
//write copyright header, including command line parameters (count == argc,
//str == argv)
void writeHeader(int count, char **str);
//Adjusts product quantities so that resources are below maximum levels if
//resource maxima are specified
void adjustAllocation(void);
//used by adjustAllocation() to reduce product quantities
int reduceProduct(int resourceIndex);
//print FM3.DAT sample to screen
void printHelp(void);

// ***** DEBUGGING AIDS *****
void db(char *str);
void db(int a);
void db(int a, int b);
void db(int a, int b, int c);
void nothing(void);

void nothing(void)
{
}

void db(char *str)
{
    printf("\nDEBUG: %s\n",str);
}

void db(int a)
{
    printf("\nDEBUG: %d\n",a);
}

void db(int a, int b)
{
    printf("\nDEBUG: %d %d\n",a,b);
}

void db(int a, int b, int c)
{
    printf("\nDEBUG: %d %d %d\n",a,b,c);
}

//*****
/***** FUNCTION DEFINITIONS *****/

```

```

int reduceProduct(int rIndex)
{
    int i = 0;
    int leastProfit = 0;
    double leastBenefit;
    while (cost[rIndex]*UC[i][rIndex] == 0.0)
    {
        //db("reduceAllocation #1");
        //nothing();
        i++;
    }
    leastBenefit = profit[i]/(cost[rIndex]*UC[i][rIndex]);
    for (i = 1; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    {
        //identifies the least profitable product to reduce to thereby reduce
        //over maximum resource quantity
        if (cost[rIndex]*UC[i][rIndex] > 0)
            if (profit[i]/(cost[rIndex]*UC[i][rIndex]) < leastBenefit)
            {
                leastBenefit = profit[i]/(cost[rIndex]*UC[i][rIndex]);
                leastProfit = i;
            }
    }
    //no reduction below the current deltaQ
    //(standard product quantity increment/decrement)
    if (QP[leastProfit] > deltaQ)
    {
        QP[leastProfit] -= deltaQ;;
        return OK; //decrement successful
    }
    else
        return BAD; //decrement not possible
}

//adjust product quantities for constrained resources
void adjustAllocation(void)
{
    int i;
    double temp;
    if (maxResourcesSpecified == NO)
        return; //return if resource maxima not specified
    for (i = 0; i < NUMRESC; i++)
    {
        while (QR[i] > maxQuantResc[i] && QR[i] > deltaQ)
        {
            calcAll();
            if (reduceProduct(i) == BAD)
                return;
        }
    }
}

void initialize(void)
{
    for (int i = 0; i < MAXELEMENTS; i++)
    {
        maxQuantResc[i] = INFINITY;
        maxQuant[i] = INFINITY;
        //minQuant[i] = -INFINITY;
        minQuant[i] = 0;
        pIsFuzzy[i] = NO;
        rIsFuzzy[i] = NO;
        QP[i] = 0.0;
    }
}

```

```

    }
}

void printTrials(int count, int bestT)
{
    fprintf(diagf, "\n_____ \n");
    fprintf(diagf, "Trials for Tableau #d\n", count);
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD*2; i++)
    {
        if (i == bestT)
            fprintf(diagf, "\n*");
        else
            fprintf(diagf, "\n ");
        fprintf(diagf, "[%d] {" , i+1);
        for (int j = 0; j < NUMPROD; j++)
            fprintf(diagf, "%g, ", trial[i].Q[j]);
        fprintf(diagf, "$%g}", trial[i].totProfit);
    }
    fprintf(diagf, "\n_____ ");
}

```

```

int readData(void)
{
    if ((df = fopen("FM3.DAT", "r")) == 0)
        return 0;
    char c = '\0';
    char chr;
    int i;
    int j;
    int total;
    char
    str[80];
    double tempr;
    NUMPROD = 0;
    NUMRESC = 0;
    while (c != '@')
    {
        c = fgetc(df);
        switch(c)
        {
            //designate comment line (ignore line)
            case ';':while(fgetc(df) != '\n')
                ;
                break;
            //set force equilibrium flag
            case 'F':forceEquilibrium = YES;
                break;
            //read maximum allowable quantities for products; if this line exists
            //all products must have mins assigned
            case '<':tempr = 0.0;
                for (j = 0; j < NUMPROD; j++)
                {
                    fscanf(df, "%s", str);
                    tempr = atof(str);
                    maxQuant[j] = tempr+0.0001;
                }
                break;
            //read maximum allowable quantities for resources; if this line exists
            //each resource must have a max assigned
            case 'M':tempr = 0.0;
                maxResourcesSpecified = YES;
                for (j = 0; j < NUMRESC; j++)

```

```

        {
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            maxQuantResc[j] = tempr+0.0001;
        }
        break;
//read minimums allowable quantities for products; if this line exists
//all products must have minsassigned
case '>':tempr = 0.0;
    for (j = 0; j < NUMPROD; j++)
    {
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        minQuant[j] = tempr-0.0001;
    }
    break;
//sets the unit resource allocations of each product
case 'U':fscanf(df,"%d",&i);
    for (j = 0; j < NUMRESC; j++)
    {
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        UC[i][j] = tempr;
    }
    break;
//product price versus quantity point description (quantity,price)
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the price is made constant for all
//practical quantities
case 'P':fscanf(df,"%d",&i);
    fscanf(df,"%c",&chr);
    if (chr == 'F')
    {
        pIsFuzzy[i] = YES;
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        zeroQPrice[i] = tempr;
        for (j = COMPETITIVE; j <= MONOPOLY; j++)
        {
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            prodIs[i][j] = tempr;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
        tempr = 0.0;
        for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
        {
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            p[i][j].quant = tempr;
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            p[i][j].val = tempr;
        }
        if (total == 1)
        {
            p[i][j].quant = INFINITY;
            p[i][j++].val = tempr;
        }
        p[i][j].quant = ENDFLAG;
    }

```

```

        p[i][j].val = ENDFLAG;
    }
    NUMPROD++;
    break;
//resource cost versus quantity point description (quantity,cost)
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the cost is made constant for all
//practical quantities
case 'R':fscanf(df,"%d",&i);
    fscanf(df,"%c",&chr);
    if (chr == 'F')
    {
        rIsFuzzy[i] = YES;
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        zeroQPrice[NUMPROD+i] = tempr;
        for (j = COMPETITIVE; i <= MONOPOLY; i++)
        {
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            prodIs[i+NUMPROD][j] = tempr;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
        tempr = 0.0;
        for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
        {
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            r[i][j].quant = tempr;
            fscanf(df,"%s",str);
            tempr = atof(str);
            r[i][j].val = tempr;
        }
        if (total == 1)
        {
            r[i][j].quant = INFINITY;
            r[i][j++].val = tempr;
        }
        r[i][j].quant = ENDFLAG;
        r[i][j].val = ENDFLAG;
    }
    NUMRESC++;
    break;
}
}
return 1;
}

//set snapshots to initial, default values
void resetTrials(void)
{
    for (int index = 0; index < NUMPROD*2; index++)
    {
        for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
            trial[index].Q[i] = 0;
        trial[index].totProfit = 0.0;
    }
}

//load trial #index to current system snapshot

```

```

void loadTrial(int index)
{
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        trial[index].Q[i] = QP[i];
    trial[index].totProfit = systemProfit;
}

//make current system the same as that of trial #index
void restoreTrial(int index)
{
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        QP[i] = trial[index].Q[i];
    calcAll();
    trial[index].totProfit = systemProfit;
}

//save snapshot of current system as the best (mostprofitable) combination
//of product quantities
void loadBest(void)
{
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        best.Q[i] = QP[i];
    best.totProfit = systemProfit;
}

//make the current system the same as the last saved best system
void restoreBest(void)
{
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        QP[i] = best.Q[i];
    calcAll();
}

//rank the most and second most profitable products for the current system
//configuration of product quantities
void calcProfitables(void)
{
    double bestProfit;
    double nextBestProfit;
    int i;
    mostProfitable = -1;
    nextMostProfitable = -1;
    bestProfit = -INFINITY;
    for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        if (profit[i] > bestProfit && QP[i] < maxQuant[i]-0.001
            && QP[i] > minQuant[i]-0.001)
        {
            bestProfit = profit[i];
            mostProfitable = i;
        }
    nextBestProfit = -INFINITY;
    for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        if (profit[i] > nextBestProfit && i != mostProfitable
            && QP[i] < maxQuant[i]-0.001
            && QP[i] > minQuant[i]-0.001)
        {
            nextBestProfit = profit[i];
            nextMostProfitable = i;
        }
}

```

```

}

//perform all calculations for the current system product quantities
void calcAll(int equilibrium)
{
    int i;
    int j;
    double mpSum = INFINITY;
    updateResourceQuantities();
    for (i = 0; i < NUMRESC; i++)
        if (rIsFuzzy[i])
            cost[i] = calcFuzzyCost(QR[i],i+NUMPROD);
        else
            cost[i] = calcCost(R, QR, i);

    for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    {
        if (pIsFuzzy[i])
            price[i] = calcFuzzyCost(QP[i],i);
        else
            price[i] = calcCost(P, QP, i);
        unitCost[i] = calcUC(i);
        profit[i] = price[i]-unitCost[i];
    }
    systemProfit = 0.0;
    for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        systemProfit += QP[i]*profit[i];

    calcProfitables();
    calcOC();
    calcMP();
    int attemptToForceCount = 0;
    if (equilibrium)
        while(mpSum > ALMOST_ZERO && attemptToForceCount < MAXFORCES)
        {
            for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
            {
                unitCost[i] = calcUC(i);
                profit[i] = price[i]-unitCost[i];
                mpSum = 0;
                calcMP();
                for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
                    mpSum += MP[i];
                for (j = 0; j < NUMPROD; j++)
                    if (QP[j] > minQuant[j] && QP[j] < maxQuant[j] && MP[j] < 0.0)
                    {
                        price[j] = price[j] - MP[j];
                        profit[j] = price[j]-unitCost[j];
                    }
            }
            systemProfit = 0.0;
            for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
                systemProfit += QP[i]*profit[i];

            calcProfitables();
            calcOC();
            calcMP();
            attemptToForceCount++;
        }
}

//calculate all unit costs according to the current system product quantities

```

```

double calcUC(int i)
{
    double temp = 0;

    for (int j = 0; j < NUMRESC; j++)
        if (!rIsFuzzy[j])
            temp += UC[i][j]*calcCost(R,QR,j);
        else
            temp += UC[i][j]*calcFuzzyCost(QR[j],j+NUMPROD);
    return temp;
}

//calculate resource costs according to the current system product quantities
double calcCost(manufactureType *E[], double *A, int index)
{
    double cost;
    cost = interpQ(E[index]->getPriorQ(A[index]),
                  E[index]->getNextQ(A[index]),
                  A[index]);
    return cost;
}

//calculate the fuzzy cost for the stated quantity for a perdefined
//fuzzy product
double calcFuzzyCost(double quantity,int index)
{
    double maxQ;
    double qAtZeroPrice;
    double cost;
    //find the centroid from the fuzzy types
    //type is the centroid of the fuzzy type memberships time 45 degrees or
    //0.785398 radians
    type = cog(index);
    alpha = type*(-0.785398);
    maxQ = -zeroQPrice[index]/(2.0*tan(alpha));
    qAtZeroPrice = -zeroQPrice[index]/tan(alpha);
    if (index > NUMPROD)
    {
        if (maxQ < maxQuantResc[index])
            maxQuantResc[index-NUMPROD] = maxQ;
    }
    else
    {
        if (maxQ < maxQuant[index])
        {
            maxQuant[index] = maxQ;
            if (QP[index] > maxQ)
                QP[index] = maxQ;
        }
    }
    if (quantity > maxQ)
        quantity = maxQ;
    cost = quantity*tan(alpha)+zeroQPrice[index];
    fprintf(diagf,
            "\nFAM->[%d] alpha:%5.2f° MAXQ:%5.2f QQ$0:%5.2f TYPE: %5.2f PRICE: %5.2f
            QUANT: %5.2f\n",
            index,alpha*180.0/3.141596535,maxQ,qAtZeroPrice,type,cost,quantity);
    return cost;
}

//simply changes the value of array A to quant
void changeQuantity(double *A, int prodIndex, double quant)

```

```

{
  A[prodIndex] = quant;
}

//counts total quantities for each resource required to support the current
//product quantities
void updateResourceQuantities(void)
{
  for (int i = 0; i < NUMRESC; i++)
  {
    QR[i] = 0.0;
    for (int j = 0; j < NUMPROD; j++)
      QR[i] += QP[j]*UC[j][i];
  }
}

//calculate all opportunity costs of each product according to the most
//and next most profitable products for the current system product quantities
void calcOC(void)
{
  int i;
  for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
  {
    if (i == mostProfitable && nextMostProfitable >= 0)
      OC[mostProfitable] = price[nextMostProfitable]*unitCost[mostProfitable]/
        unitCost[nextMostProfitable]
        -unitCost[mostProfitable];
    else if (i == nextMostProfitable && mostProfitable >= 0)
      OC[nextMostProfitable] =
price[mostProfitable]*unitCost[nextMostProfitable]/
        unitCost[mostProfitable]
        -unitCost[nextMostProfitable];
    else if (mostProfitable >= 0)
      OC[i] = price[mostProfitable]*unitCost[i]/
        unitCost[mostProfitable]
        -unitCost[i];
    else
      OC[i] = 0.0;
  }
}

//calculate all marginal profits for each product for the current
//system quantities
void calcMP(void)
{
  for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    MP[i] = price[i]-OC[i]-unitCost[i];
}

//take snapshots (trials) of each system as each product quantity is
//individually decremented by the standard amount deltaQ
void nextIterateDown(void)
{
  for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    if (MP[i] < 0)
    {
      double temp = QP[i]-deltaQ;
      if (temp > minQuant[i])
      {
        restoreTrial(2*NUMPROD);
      }
    }
}

```

```

        changeQuantity(QP,i,temp);
        calcAll();
        loadTrial(i);
    }
}
calcAll();
}

//take snapshots (trials) of each system as each product quantity is
//individually incremented by the standard amount deltaQ
void nextIterateUp(void)
{
    {
        for (int i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
            if (MP[i] > 0)
            {
                double temp = QP[i]+deltaQ;
                if (temp < maxQuant[i])
                {
                    restoreTrial(2*NUMPROD);
                    changeQuantity(QP,i,temp);
                    calcAll();
                    adjustAllocation();
                    loadTrial(2*i);
                }
            }
    }
    calcAll();
}

//print tableaus to output file f (defaults to stdout)
void printData(FILE *f)
{
    int i;
    int offset = NUMRESC;
    if (NUMRESC > 7)
        offset = 5;
    fprintf(f,"\n\nRESC  ");
    for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
        fprintf(f,"#%-10d",i+1);
    fprintf(f,"\nQUANT  ");
    for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    {
        if (QR[i] < maxQuantResc[i])
            fprintf(f," %-10.0f",QR[i]);
        else
            fprintf(f,"!%-10.0f",QR[i]);
    }
    fprintf(f,"\nCOST  ");
    for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
        fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",cost[i]);

    if (NUMRESC > 7)
    {
        fprintf(f,"\n\nRESC  ");
        for (i = offset; i < NUMRESC; i++)
            fprintf(f,"#%-10d",i+1);
        fprintf(f,"\nQUANT  ");
        for (i = offset; i < NUMRESC; i++)
        {
            if (QR[i] < maxQuantResc[i])
                fprintf(f," %-10.0f",QR[i]);
            else

```

```

    fprintf(f,"!%-10.0f",QR[i]);
}
fprintf(f,"\nCOST  ");
for (i = offset; i < NUMRESC; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",cost[i]);
}

fprintf(f,"\n\nPROD  ");

offset = NUMPROD;
if (NUMPROD > 7)
    offset = 5;

for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"#%-10d",i+1);
fprintf(f,"\nQUANT  ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
{
    if (maxQuant[i] >= QP[i])
        fprintf(f," %-10.0f",QP[i]);
    else
        fprintf(f,"!%-10.0f",QP[i]);
}
fprintf(f,"\nPRICE  ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",price[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nUC      ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",unitCost[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nOC      ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",OC[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nMP      ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",MP[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nPROFIT ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",profit[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nTOTPRF ");
for (i = 0; i < offset; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",profit[i]*QP[i]);
// fprintf(f,"\n\nTotal Profit: $%-10.2f",systemProfit);

if (NUMPROD > 7)
{
    fprintf(f,"\n\nPROD  ");
    for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        fprintf(f,"#%-10d",i+1);
    fprintf(f,"\nQUANT  ");
    for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    {
        if (maxQuant[i] >= QP[i])
            fprintf(f,"!%-10.0f",QP[i]);
        else
            fprintf(f," %-10.0f!",QP[i]);
    }
    fprintf(f,"\nPRICE  ");
    for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",price[i]);
    fprintf(f,"\nUC      ");
    for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
        fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",unitCost[i]);
    fprintf(f,"\nOC      ");
}

```

```

for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",OC[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nMP      ");
for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",MP[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nPROFIT ");
for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",profit[i]);
fprintf(f,"\nTOTPRF ");
for (i = offset; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    fprintf(f,"$%-10.2f",profit[i]*QP[i]);
}

fprintf(f,"\n\nTotal Profit: $%-10.2f",systemProfit);

if (!singleRun)
    fprintf(f,"\nQuantity Increment: %d",deltaQ);
fprintf(f,"\n_____ \n");
}

//assign all product and resource arrays to manufactureType instances
void setupR_Ps(void)
{
    int i;
    for (i = 0; i < NUMRESC; i++)
    {
        if (!rIsFuzzy[i])
        {
            R[i] = new manufactureType(r[i]);
            // R[i]->list();
        }
    }
    for (i = 0; i < NUMPROD; i++)
    {
        if (!pIsFuzzy[i])
        {
            P[i] = new manufactureType(p[i]);
            // P[i]->list();
        }
    }
}

//write header information to the diagnostics file and stdout
void writeHeader(int count, char **s)
{
    int i;
    char str[255] = {0};
    int length;
    for (i = 1; i < count; i++)
    {
        strcat(str,s[i]);
        strcat(str," ");
    }
    length = strlen(str);

fprintf(diagf,"\n_____ \n");
fprintf(diagf,"Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility \n");
fprintf(diagf,"Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranic \n");
fprintf(diagf,"COMMAND LINE: %s",str);
for (i = 0; i < 41-length; i++)
    fprintf(diagf," ");
fprintf(diagf,

```

```

    "||\n\|_____| \n\n");
printf("\n\|_____| \n");
printf("||Fuzzy Microeconomic Modeling of Manufacturing Utility ||\n");
printf("||Copyright 1996, Steven F. Srebranig ||\n");
printf("||COMMAND LINE: %s",str);
for (i = 0; i < 41-length; i++)
    printf(" ");
printf("||\n\|_____| \n\n");
}

//write format information to stdout
void printHelp(void)
{
    printf("\nFORMAT: FM3 <deltaQ> <MAXQP1> <MAXQP2> <MAXP3> <NUMITERATIONS>");
    printf("\nOR FORMAT: FM3 S <QP1> <QP2> <QP3> <--single tableau");
    printf("\nFM3.DAT file contains initialization data, a sample follows:");
    printf("\n    {Strike 'C' to continue...}");
    while (!(toupper(getch()) == 'C'))
        ;
    clrscr();
    printf("\n;a semicolon designates a comment to ignore");
    printf("\n;the P and R lines must come first in the FM3.DAT file");
    printf("\n;product price descriptions (10 max, P0 through P9 in sequence)");
    printf("\n;product prices are fuzzy if the third character is 'F', not '
");
    printf("\nP0 7 0 20 10 20 20 12.5 30 7.5 120 7.5 130 5 1000000 5");
    printf("\n;P1F is fuzzy, stating 95% competitive, 10% competitive_monopoly");
    printf("\n;    1% oligopoly and 0% monopoly");
    printf("\nP1F 0.95 0.10 0.01 0.0");
    printf("\n;resource cost descriptions (10 max, R0 through R9 in sequence)");
    printf("\nR0 4 0 2 50 2 60 1 1000000 1");
    printf("\nR1 6 0 3 70 3 80 2 90 2 100 1 1000000 1");
    printf("\n    {Strike 'C' to continue...}");
    while (!(toupper(getch()) == 'C'))
        ;
    clrscr();
    printf("\n;unit cost descriptions for each product");
    printf("\nU0 2 1");
    printf("\nU1 1 5");
    printf("\n;optional maximum resource values, if an M line exists, all max's
are needed");
    printf("\nM 400 400");
    printf("\n;optional max product quantities, if an < line exists, all max's
are needed");
    printf("\n< 200 200");
    printf("\n;optional min product quantities, if an > line exists, all min's
are needed");
    printf("\n> 0 0");
    printf("\n;the optional F line denotes that equilibrium is to be forced for
every tableau");
    printf("\nF");
    printf("\n;@ is necessary and designates end of file");
    printf("\n@\n");
}

/***** MAIN *****/

int main(int argc, char **argv)

```



```

    }
    numberOfIterations = atoi(argv[NUMPROD+2]);
    if (numberOfIterations == 0)
        numberOfIterations = 1;

    setupR_Ps();

    writeHeader(argc, argv);

    printf("\n[TABLEAU #1]");
    calcAll();
    adjustAllocation();
    calcAll();
    loadBest();
    bestTableau = 1;
    printData();
    if (forceEquilibrium)
    {
        calcAll(YES);
        printf("\n[BEST TABLEAU #%d], forcing equilibrium",bestTableau);
        printData();
        calcAll();
    }
    restoreBest();
    int trialCount;
    for (int j = 0; j < numberOfIterations-1; j++)
    {
        resetTrials();
        loadTrial(2*NUMPROD); //snap shot of current quantities
        nextIterateDown();
        nextIterateUp();
        int bestTrial = 0;
        double tempr = 0.0;
        for (trialCount = 0; trialCount < NUMPROD*2; trialCount++)
        {
            if (tempr < trial[trialCount].totProfit)
            {
                tempr = trial[trialCount].totProfit;
                bestTrial = trialCount;
            }
        }
        if (trial[bestTrial].totProfit != 0.0)
        {
            recentProfit[recentCount++] = trial[bestTrial].totProfit;
            recentCount = recentCount % 3;
            restoreTrial(bestTrial);
            if (best.totProfit < trial[bestTrial].totProfit)
            {
                best = trial[bestTrial]; //loadBest();
                bestTableau = j+2;
                printf("*");
            }
        }
        if (recentProfit[0] == recentProfit[1]
            || recentProfit[1] == recentProfit[2]
            || recentProfit[0] == recentProfit[2])
            if (retried < MAXRETRIES && deltaQ > 1)
            {
                recentProfit[0] = -1000.0;
                recentProfit[1] = -2000.0;
                recentProfit[2] = -3000.0;
                restoreBest(); //retry at best Tableau so far
                deltaQ /= 2;
            }
    }

```

```

printf("\nRessetting to Previous BEST Tableau; Q increment is now: %d",
      deltaQ);
fprintf(diagf, "\nNEW Q increment: %d\n", deltaQ);
printData();
retried++;
}
else
{
printf("\n
Tableaus have become DEGENERATE; stopping system...
");
puts( "\n
");
j = numberOfIterations;
stopProgram = YES;
}
printTrials(j+2, bestTrial);
}
else
{
if (retried < MAXRETRIES && deltaQ > 1)
{
restoreBest(); //retry at best Tableau so far
deltaQ /= 2;
printf("\nRessetting to Previous BEST Tableau; Q increment is now: %d",
      deltaQ);
fprintf(diagf, "\nNEW Q increment: %d\n", deltaQ);
printData();
retried++;
}
else
{
restoreTrial(2*NUMPROD);
printf("\nNO IMPROVEMENT at TABLEAU #%d; stopping system...\n", j+2);
j = numberOfIterations;
stopProgram = YES;
}
}
if (!stopProgram)
{
printf("\n[TABLEAU #%d]", j+2);
printData();
if (forceEquilibrium)
{
calcAll(YES);
printf("\n[TABLEAU #%d], forcing equilibrium", j+2);
printData();
calcAll();
}
}
}
restoreBest();
printf("\n
");
printf("\nBEST Tableau was #%d:", bestTableau);
printData();
if (forceEquilibrium)
{
calcAll(YES);
printf("\n[BEST TABLEAU #%d], forcing equilibrium", bestTableau);
printData();
calcAll();
}
}
fclose(diagf);
return 0;
}

```

MANUF.HPP

```

#ifndef MANUF_HPP
#define MANUF_HPP

#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <conio.h>
#include <mem.h>

#define ENDFLAG -1

class manufactureType;

typedef struct element {
    double quant;
    double val;
};

typedef struct massType {
    double mass;
    double xmass;
};

double interpVal(element m1, element m2, double val);
double interpQ(element m1, element m2, double Q);

// base class type for products and resources based on
class manufactureType {
    element *m;
    int lastM;
    double Quantity;
    double maxQ;
    double minQ;
    double maxVal;
    int norm;
public:
    manufactureType(element *memberArray, int normalize = 0);
    ~manufactureType(void);
    manufactureType(int normalize = 0);
    void reset(element *memberArray);
    double getMembership(double quant);
    int setQuantity(double Q) {Quantity = Q; return 0;};
    int getQuantPrior(double quant);
    int getQuantNext(double quant);
    double getMaxQ(void) {return maxQ;};
    double getMinQ(void) {return minQ;};
    massType calcMass(double memberVal);
    element getNextQ(double quant);
    element getNextVal(double val);
    element getPriorQ(double quant);
    element getPriorVal(double val);
    element getM(int i);

    void list(void);
};

#endif

```

MANUF.CPP

```

#include "manuf.hpp"

manufactureType::manufactureType(element *memberArray,int normalize)
{
    norm = normalize;
    maxVal = 0.0;
    int i = 0;
    m = new element[25];
    while (memberArray[i].val != ENDFLAG)
        {
            m[i].quant = memberArray[i].quant;
            m[i].val = memberArray[i].val;
            if (maxVal < m[i].val)
                maxVal = m[i].val;
            i++;
        }
    lastM = i;
    if (norm)
        for (i = 0; i < lastM; i++)
            m[i].val /= maxVal;
    maxQ = 0;
    minQ = 0;
    Quantity = 0;
}

manufactureType::~manufactureType(void)
{
    delete m;
}

manufactureType::manufactureType(int normalize)
{
    norm = normalize;
}

void manufactureType::reset(element *memberArray)
{
    maxVal = 0.0;
    int i = 0;
    m = new element[25];
    while (memberArray[i].val != ENDFLAG)
        {
            m[i].quant = memberArray[i].quant;
            m[i].val = memberArray[i].val;
            if (maxVal < m[i].val)
                maxVal = m[i].val;
            i++;
        }
    lastM = i;
    if (norm)
        for (i = 0; i < lastM; i++)
            m[i].val /= maxVal;
    maxQ = 0;
    minQ = 0;
    Quantity = 0;
}

double manufactureType::getMembership(double Q)
{

```

```

int i = 0;
if (Q <= m[0].quant)
    return m[0].val;
while (i < lastM)
{
    if (m[i].quant > Q)
        break;
    i++;
}
if (Q >= m[lastM-1].quant)
    return m[lastM-1].val;
double returnVal = interpQ(m[i-1],m[i],Q);
return returnVal;
}

void manufactureType::list(void)
{
    cprintf("\n\r");
    for (int i = 0; i < lastM; i++)
        cprintf("\n\rQUANTITIY:%g MEMBERSHIP:%g",m[i].quant,m[i].val);
}

element manufactureType::getM(int i)
{
    if (i < lastM)
        return m[i];
    else
        return m[lastM-1];
};

//calcs mass and x*mass, or xmass (returning type massType) using every
//point in the description of the curve; te more points there are,
//the more precise the calculation of mass and xmass, in particular,
//the center of gravity, cog = xmass/mass
massType manufactureType::calcMass(double memberVal)
{
    massType temp = {0.0,0.0};
    for (int i = 0; i < lastM; i++)
    {
        if (memberVal < m[i].val)
        {
            temp.mass += memberVal;
            temp.xmass += m[i].quant*memberVal;
        }
        else
        {
            temp.mass += m[i].val;
            temp.xmass += m[i].quant*m[i].val;
        }
    }
    return temp;
}

int manufactureType::getQuantNext(double Q)
{
    int i = 0;
    while (Q > m[i].quant && i < lastM)
        i++;
    return i;
}

int manufactureType::getQuantPrior(double Q)

```

```

{
  int i = lastM-1;
  while (Q < m[i].quant && i >= 0)
    i--;
  return i;
}

element manufactureType::getNextQ(double Q)
{
  int i = 0;
  while (Q > m[i].quant && i < lastM)
    i++;
  return m[i];
}

element manufactureType::getNextVal(double V)
{
  int i = 0;
  while (V > m[i].val && i < lastM)
    i++;
  return m[i];
}

element manufactureType::getPriorQ(double Q)
{
  int i = lastM-1;
  while (Q < m[i].quant && i >= 0)
    i--;
  return m[i];
}

element manufactureType::getPriorVal(double V)
{
  int i = lastM-1;
  while (V < m[i].val && i >= 0)
    i--;
  return m[i];
}

//linear interpolation for val between m1 and m2
double interpVal(element m1, element m2, double val)
{
  if (m1.quant == m2.quant)
    return m1.quant;
  double slope = (m2.quant - m1.quant)/(m2.val - m1.val);
  return (val - m1.val)*slope+m1.quant;
}

//linear interpolation for quant between m1 and m2
double interpQ(element m1, element m2, double Q)
{
  double returnVal;
  if (m1.val == m2.val)
    return m1.val;
  double slope = (m2.val - m1.val)/(m2.quant - m1.quant);
  returnVal = (Q - m1.quant)*slope+m1.val;
  return returnVal;
}

```


FAM.HPP

```

/*****
#endif
#define FAM_HPP

//FAM for Fuzzy Certainty to product type tranformation
//Steven F. Srebranig 1-1-96

#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <ctype.h>
#include "manuf.hpp"

#define MAXPOINTS 20
#define MAXELEMENTS 10
#define MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS 20

extern manufactureType *mType[MONOPOLY+1];
extern manufactureType *sureOf;

//microeconomic type curve descriptions
extern element pt_COMPETITIVE[];
extern element pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[];
extern element pt_OLIGOPOLY[];
extern element pt_MONOPOLY[];

extern element cert[];

//prod(uct)Is(how much, between 0 and 1,the product can be described by the
//particular miroeconomic type
extern double prodIs[MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS][MONOPOLY+1];

//microeconomic type curve descriptions in array form
extern element pt[MONOPOLY+1][MAXPOINTS];

extern double zeroQPrice[MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS];

//global definition so that mass and xmass are available external to the
//cog() function
extern massType mass;

//copies product type curves into a contiguous array
void setupProductTypes(void);

//lists product descriptions
void showProdTypes(void);

//calculates the center of gravity (product type fraction between perfect
//competition (0.0) to perfect monopoly (1.00)
double cog(int ID);

//assigns membership values to each microeconomic type for product/resource
// with index ID
void assignProdDesc(int ID, double C, double CM, double O, double M);

//routine to read a file containing microeconomic type descriptions
int readTypes(char *dataFileName);

```

```
#endif
```

FAM.CPP

```

/*****
//FAM for Fuzzy Certainty to product type tranformation

#include "general.hpp"
#include "fam.hpp"

double prodIs[MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS][MONOPOLY+1];
element pt[MONOPOLY+1][MAXPOINTS];

manufactureType *mType[MONOPOLY+1];
manufactureType *sureOf;

//microeconomic type curve descriptions
element pt_COMPETITIVE[MAXPOINTS];
element pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[MAXPOINTS];
element pt_OLIGOPOLY[MAXPOINTS];
element pt_MONOPOLY[MAXPOINTS];

//certainty curve description
element cert[MAXPOINTS];

double zeroQPrice[MAXRESOURCESANDPRODUCTS];

int readTypes(char *fname)
{
    FILE *df;
    if ((df = fopen(fname,"r")) == 0)
        return 0;
    char c = '\0';
    // int i;
    int j;
    int total;
    char str[80];
    double tempr;
    while (c != '@')
    {
        c = fgetc(df);
        switch(c)
        {
            //designate comment line (ignore line)
            case ';':while(fgetc(df) != '\n')
                ;
                break;
            //COMPETITIVE type membership versus percent type (0 = perfectly
            //competitive; 1.0 = perfectly monopolistic) quantity point description
            //first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
            //if only one is specified, the membership curve is made constant
            case 'C':fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
                tempr = 0.0;
                for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
                {
                    fscanf(df,"%s",str);
                    tempr = atof(str);
                    pt_COMPETITIVE[j].quant = tempr;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

fscanf(df,"%s",str);
tempr = atof(str);
pt_COMPETITIVE[j].val = tempr;
}
if (total == 1)
{
pt_COMPETITIVE[j].quant = INFINITY;
pt_COMPETITIVE[j++].val = tempr;
}
pt_COMPETITIVE[j].quant = ENDFLAG;
pt_COMPETITIVE[j++].val = ENDFLAG;
break;
//COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY type membership versus percent type (0 = perfectly
//competitive; 1.0 = perfectly monopolistic) quantity point description
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the membership curve is made constant
case 'B':fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
tempr = 0.0;
for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
{
fscanf(df,"%s",str);
tempr = atof(str);
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j].quant = tempr;
fscanf(df,"%s",str);
tempr = atof(str);
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j].val = tempr;
}
if (total == 1)
{
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j].quant = INFINITY;
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j++].val = tempr;
}
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j].quant = ENDFLAG;
pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY[j++].val = ENDFLAG;
break;
//OLIGOPOLY type membership versus percent type (0 = perfectly
//competitive; 1.0 = perfectly monopolistic) quantity point description
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the membership curve is made constant
case 'O':fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
tempr = 0.0;
for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
{
fscanf(df,"%s",str);
tempr = atof(str);
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j].quant = tempr;
fscanf(df,"%s",str);
tempr = atof(str);
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j].val = tempr;
}
if (total == 1)
{
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j].quant = INFINITY;
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j++].val = tempr;
}
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j].quant = ENDFLAG;
pt_OLIGOPOLY[j++].val = ENDFLAG;
break;
//MONOPOLY type membership versus percent type (0 = perfectly
//competitive; 1.0 = perfectly monopolistic) quantity point description
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the membership curve is made constant
case 'M':fscanf(df,"%d",&total);

```

```

    tempr = 0.0;
    for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
    {
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        pt_MONOPOLY[j].quant = tempr;
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        pt_MONOPOLY[j].val = tempr;
    }
    if (total == 1)
    {
        pt_MONOPOLY[j].quant = INFINITY;
        pt_MONOPOLY[j++].val = tempr;
    }
    pt_MONOPOLY[j].quant = ENDFLAG;
    pt_MONOPOLY[j++].val = ENDFLAG;
    break;
//certainty (sureOf) type membership versus percent type (0 = perfectly
//competitive; 1.0 = perfectly monopolistic) quantity point description
//first parameter identifies the number of points to scan
//if only one is specified, the membership curve is made constant
case 'S':fscanf(df,"%d",&total);
    tempr = 0.0;
    for (j = 0; j < total; j++)
    {
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        cert[j].quant = tempr;
        fscanf(df,"%s",str);
        tempr = atof(str);
        cert[j].val = tempr;
    }
    if (total == 1)
    {
        cert[j].quant = INFINITY;
        cert[j++].val = tempr;
    }
    cert[j].quant = ENDFLAG;
    cert[j++].val = ENDFLAG;
    break;
}
}
fclose(df);
return 1;
}

//global definition so that mass and xmass are available external to the
//cog() function
massType mass;

//copies product type curves into a contiguous array
void setupProductTypes(void)
{
    int i;
    memcpy(pt[COMPETITIVE],pt_COMPETITIVE,sizeof(pt_COMPETITIVE));

    memcpy(pt[COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY],pt_COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY,sizeof(pt_COMPETITIVE_M
ONOPOLY));
    memcpy(pt[OLIGOPOLY],pt_OLIGOPOLY,sizeof(pt_OLIGOPOLY));
    memcpy(pt[MONOPOLY],pt_MONOPOLY,sizeof(pt_MONOPOLY));
    sureOf = new manufactureType(cert);
    for (i = 0; i <= MONOPOLY; i++)

```

```

    mType[i] = new manufactureType(pt[i]);
}

void showProdTypes(void)
{
    int i;
    for (i = 0; i <= MONOPOLY; i++)
    {
        switch(i)
        {
            case COMPETITIVE:printf("\n\nCOMPETITIVE:"); break;
            case COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY:printf("\n\nCOMPETITIVE MONOPOLY:"); break;
            case OLIGOPOLY:printf("\n\nOLIGOPOLY:"); break;
            case MONOPOLY:printf("\n\nMONOPOLY:"); break;
        }
        mType[i]->list();
    }
    puts("\n\nCertainty:");
    sureOf->list();
}

//calculates the center of gravity (product type fraction between perfect
//competition (0.0) to perfect monopoly (1.00)
double cog(int ID)
{
    // massType temp;
    mass.mass = 0.0;
    mass.xmass = 0.0;

    for (int i = 0; i <= MONOPOLY; i++)
    {
        massType temp;

        //get membership for item for specific type description
        double PRODIS = prodIs[ID][i];
        //calc mass and xmass for certainty (sureOf) adjusted membership
        temp = mType[i]->calcMass(PRODIS*sureOf->getMembership(PRODIS));
        //accumulate mass' and xmass'
        mass.xmass += temp.xmass;
        mass.mass += temp.mass;
    }

    mass.mass += 1e-25;
    //return center of gravity of all types together
    return mass.xmass/mass.mass;
}

//assigns membership values to each microeconomic type for product/resource
// with index ID
void assignProdDesc(int ID, double C, double CM, double O, double M)
{
    prodIs[ID][COMPETITIVE] = C;
    prodIs[ID][COMPETITIVE_MONOPOLY] = CM;
    prodIs[ID][OLIGOPOLY] = O;
    prodIs[ID][MONOPOLY] = M;
}

/*
int main(void)
{
    int i;
    clrscr();
    setupProductTypes();
}

```

```
assignProdDesc(0, .25, .9, .45, .1);
sureOf->list();
puts("");

printf("cog = %g", cog(0));

return 0;
}
*/
```

APPENDIX B

Product Type Identification

Concerning the specified product, please indicate to what extent you agree, in percent from 0 (totally disagree) to 100 (totally agree), with the following statements:

The product is **perfectly competitive** _____%

The product is **perfectly monopolistic** _____%

The product is a **competitive monopoly** _____%

The product is an **oligopoly** _____%

Perfectly Competitive means the price of the product does not change regardless of the quantities of the product that is purchased; there are numerous producers of the product.

Perfectly Monopolistic means the price of the product changes with any increase or decrease of the quantity of the product that is purchased; there is essentially only a single producer of the product.

Competitive Monopoly means the price of a product is consistent but can change due to large changes in the quantities purchased of the product; there are typically several producers of the product.

Oligopoly means the price of a product is largely dependent upon the quantities purchased of the product; there are typically few producers of the product.

APPENDIX C

Certainty Survey

Below are nine horizontal bars with two sections each bar. The left section is shaded; the right section is not shaded. In the right section of each bar write, in percent between 0 and 100, how WHITE the left bar is.

APPENDIX D

Survey Data

	Survey #1	Survey #2	Survey #3	Survey #4	Survey #5	Survey #6	MEAN	STD DEV
P0								
Perfect Competition	0.00	5.00	50.00	20.00	0.00	100.00	29.17	39.55
Perfect Monopoly	0.00	5.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	2.04
Competitive Monopoly	50.00	80.00	100.00	80.00	50.00	85.00	74.17	20.10
Oligopoly	50.00	10.00	50.00	50.00	80.00	20.00	43.33	25.03
P1								
Perfect Competition	0.00	5.00	50.00	20.00	0.00	100.00	29.17	39.55
Perfect Monopoly	0.00	5.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	2.04
Competitive Monopoly	50.00	80.00	100.00	80.00	50.00	70.00	71.67	19.41
Oligopoly	50.00	10.00	50.00	50.00	80.00	40.00	46.67	22.51
P2								
Perfect Competition	0.00	5.00	50.00	20.00	0.00	10.00	14.17	19.08
Perfect Monopoly	0.00	5.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	95.00	16.67	38.43
Competitive Monopoly	50.00	80.00	100.00	80.00	50.00	40.00	66.67	23.38
Oligopoly	50.00	10.00	50.00	50.00	80.00	95.00	55.83	29.40
P3								
Perfect Competition	0.00	5.00	50.00	20.00	90.00	0.00	27.50	36.02
Perfect Monopoly	0.00	35.00	0.00	0.00	70.00	100.00	34.17	42.71
Competitive Monopoly	50.00	50.00	100.00	50.00	50.00	10.00	51.67	28.58
Oligopoly	50.00	10.00	50.00	80.00	30.00	80.00	50.00	27.57
P4								
Perfect Competition	0.00	10.00	50.00	20.00	0.00	95.00	29.17	37.20
Perfect Monopoly	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	8.33	13.29
Competitive Monopoly	50.00	50.00	100.00	80.00	50.00	80.00	68.33	21.37
Oligopoly	50.00	10.00	50.00	50.00	80.00	60.00	50.00	22.80
CERTAINTY WHITE	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	3.50	1.87
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12.50	0.00	0.00	12.50	2.00	10.00	1.00	4.25	5.53
25.00	0.00	10.00	25.00	3.00	30.00	3.00	11.83	12.67
37.50	2.00	30.00	37.50	15.00	40.00	8.00	22.08	15.96
50.00	5.00	50.00	50.00	20.00	50.00	10.00	30.83	21.54
62.50	10.00	60.00	62.50	30.00	60.00	15.00	39.58	24.21
75.00	40.00	80.00	75.00	40.00	70.00	20.00	54.17	24.17

87.50	50.00	95.00	87.50	50.00	80.00	25.00	64.58	27.13
100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
CERTAINTY BLACK	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	3.50	1.87
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12.50	5.00	12.50	50.00	10.00	30.00	50.00	26.25	20.23
25.00	30.00	25.00	60.00	20.00	60.00	60.00	42.50	19.43
37.50	50.00	37.50	70.00	30.00	80.00	90.00	59.58	24.10
50.00	70.00	50.00	80.00	50.00	85.00	95.00	71.67	18.62
62.50	80.00	62.50	85.00	60.00	90.00	98.00	79.25	15.18
75.00	90.00	75.00	97.00	70.00	95.00	100.00	87.83	12.42
87.50	95.00	87.50	98.00	85.00	98.00	100.00	93.92	6.20
100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
CERTAINTY GRAY	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	3.50	1.87
0.00	35.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.83	14.29
25.00	42.50	12.50	51.00	17.50	6.00	50.00	29.92	20.18
50.00	70.00	37.50	54.00	40.00	15.00	45.00	43.58	18.30
75.00	85.00	75.00	70.00	70.00	80.00	45.00	70.83	13.93
100.00	90.00	100.00	80.00	100.00	90.00	30.00	81.67	26.39

APPENDIX E

Product Price Structure

Product Quantity	1.00	10.00	50.00	100.00	250.00	500.00	1000.00
P0 Price (Each)	\$14.50	\$12.00	\$11.00	\$10.25	\$8.70	\$7.90	\$5.30
P1 Price (Each)	\$15.00	\$12.50	\$11.50	\$10.75	\$9.20	\$8.40	\$5.80
P2 Price (Each)	\$15.00	\$12.50	\$11.50	\$10.75	\$9.20	\$8.40	\$5.80
P3 Price (Each)	\$17.50	\$15.00	\$13.50	\$12.30	\$10.50	\$9.50	\$8.95
P4 Price (Each)	\$18.00	\$15.50	\$14.00	\$12.80	\$11.00	\$9.45	\$9.45

APPENDIX F

Resource Costs (Unit Cost per Stated Quantity)

R0 Quantity	Cost	R1 Quantity	Cost	R2 Quantity	Cost	R3 Quantity	Cost
0.00	\$0.08	0.00	\$0.05	0.00	\$0.11	0.00	\$0.02
52.04	\$0.08	52.04	\$0.05	50.41	\$0.11	200.00	\$0.02
71.26	\$0.08	71.26	\$0.05	71.08	\$0.11	1000.00	\$0.02
76.43	\$0.08	76.43	\$0.05	88.76	\$0.11	2000.00	\$0.02
100.80	\$0.08	100.80	\$0.05	102.73	\$0.11	4000.00	\$0.01
103.43	\$0.08	103.43	\$0.05	136.96	\$0.10	1000000.00	\$0.01
121.62	\$0.07	121.62	\$0.04	163.10	\$0.10		
144.46	\$0.08	144.46	\$0.05	203.24	\$0.10		
155.81	\$0.08	155.81	\$0.05	249.19	\$0.11		
201.15	\$0.08	201.15	\$0.05	251.67	\$0.11		
R4 Quantity	Cost	R5 Quantity	Cost	R6 Quantity	Cost	R7 Quantity	Cost
0.00	\$0.04	0.00	\$0.17	0.00	\$0.48	0.00	\$1.32
200.00	\$0.04	1.00	\$0.17	1.00	\$0.48	1.00	\$1.32
1000.00	\$0.03	9.00	\$0.17	9.00	\$0.48	9.00	\$1.32
2000.00	\$0.02	10.00	\$0.16	10.00	\$0.45	10.00	\$1.24
5000.00	\$0.02	99.00	\$0.16	99.00	\$0.45	99.00	\$1.24
		100.00	\$0.14	100.00	\$0.41	100.00	\$1.13
		1000.00	\$0.14	1000.00	\$0.41	1000.00	\$1.13
R8 Quantity	Cost	R9 Quantity	Cost				
0.00	\$2.28	0.00	\$0.36				
1.00	\$2.28	100.00	\$0.36				
9.00	\$2.28	200.00	\$0.36				
10.00	\$2.14	300.00	\$0.36				
99.00	\$2.14	400.00	\$0.36				
100.00	\$1.96	500.00	\$0.36				
1000.00	\$1.96	600.00	\$0.36				
		700.00	\$0.36				
		800.00	\$0.36				
		900.00	\$0.36				
		1000.00	\$0.36				

APPENDIX G

Using the Software Utility

The software utility, FM3, automates the FM³ algorithm and requires two input files: FM3.DAT and FM3.TYP. These input files are line commands for FM3 and each start with specific character, denoting the definition of the line command or a semi colon, denoting a non-executable remark or comment; white spaces are ignored.

FM3.DAT describes the resource and product domains and unit costs for each product. A maximum of ten resources and a maximum of ten products are allowed. Product line commands begin with the character P followed by a digit, 0 through 9, and must be in sequence. Similarly for the resources, character R and unit costs, character U. The product line commands must precede those for unit costs because FM3 uses the count of products in the product domain to determine the number of coefficients to scan in the unit cost line command.

The line commands for resources and product have the same format: the first number denotes the quantity of successive graph points and the remaining numbers are quantity/prices pairs. An example line command for P3 could be:

P3 2 0 5 1000 0

and means, to FM3, that product #3 (fourth product, the first one being #0), is described by two points; the first point is (0,5), or at quantity 0, the product price is \$5.00; the second point is (1000,0), signifying the 1000 piece quantity price of \$0. The two points describe a single line between the two points. Any amount of points can be used as long as the first number of the line command corresponds.

Alternately, a product may be specified as having a fuzzy product type. In this case, the character F must directly follow the product designation, such as P0F for product 0. The initial product price then four numbers follow the product designation. The four numbers represent the percent membership in each of the following four product types: competitive, competitive-monopoly, oligopoly, and monopoly. For example, P3F 8 34 56 78 90 designates that product 3 has an initial price of \$8.00 and is 34% competitive, 56% competitive-monopoly, 78% oligopoly, and 90% monopoly. Note that the total of all four percentages need not be 100%, though it may seem sensible to be so; since the fuzzy output is based on the centroid of the four values it is only necessary that the percentages are relative to one another.

An example of a unit cost line command for product 2 is shown below:

U2 0 0 1 2

This signifies that the resource cost of product 2 includes nothing of resources 0 and 1, one of resource 3 and two of resource 4.

Maximum product quantities may be specified by using the < character followed by a stated maximum for each quantity. If one or more products has no limit, a very large, unattainable value must be used as its maximum. Minimum product quantities may also be specified by using the > character followed by a stated minimum for each quantity. If one or more products has no limit, 0 should be specified.

Resource maxima are specified with the M character, and if this line command exists, every resource must have a maximum stated. If a resource does not have an actual maximum, then some large and unattainable value should be used.

The character F, a single character line command, designates that FM3 should attempt to force all product marginal profits to zero, thus forcing equilibrium, on every tableau that is generated.

The input file FM3.TYP contains the descriptions of the curves for each of the four product types and an additional curve description that is used to gauge and transform the fuzzy product percentage descriptions of FM3.DAT into unbiased percentages.

APPENDIX H

Review of Microeconomics

Microeconomic theory defines four basic product types: *perfect competition*, *competitive-monopoly*, *oligopoly*, and *monopoly*. Perfect competition (or simply, competition) and monopoly are the limiting types; competitive-monopoly and oligopoly derive characteristics from both.

...economists use the term *competition* in the narrow sense to refer to an industry in which all firms are price takers...a monopoly is a one-firm industry in the technical sense that a monopolist can set the price of his product without having to take into account the responses of firms selling similar or related products.⁹

A perfectly competitive market has a pricing structure that is general in makeup. That is, the lowest levels of the market, the consumers, providers of key resources, and so on, are the sole definers of the price. No producer or consumer has any market influence individually, and each producer and consumer is essentially anonymous; the price and the quality of the products in the market are the only knowable attributes. There are also no explicit exclusions of producers or resources for the perfectly competitive market.

In a perfectly competitive market, firms are essentially units of manufacturing that take inputs and create outputs. Since the participants in the market lack any market power, price

⁹ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 339.

cannot be adjusted by bidding or negotiating between them. There are no means for price wars or collusion. Every participant is a *price taker* rather than a *price maker* [Quirk, 1987].

At the other end of the microeconomic spectrum is the monopoly.

*A pure monopoly exists when an industry consists of only one firm; the pure monopoly firm is the only producer and seller of the industry's product. As contrasted with the competitive firm, the monopoly firm chooses an output and an associated price for his product.*¹⁰

As can be seen from the equations of Chapter 3 (3-11), a linear demand curve for a monopolist means demand is inelastic at low prices and elastic at high prices [Quirk, 1987].

*A profit-maximizing pure monopoly firm will never operate at a price and level of output such that the demand curve is inelastic at that output. This is because if the demand happens to be elastic, producing less product increases revenue since the quantity produced is greater than the average quantity; but a decrease in quantity means less cost of production--profits can then increase even though less is made to sell. A monopoly cannot then optimize profits at a particular quantity for an inelastic demand at that quantity...The demand curve facing a monopoly firm is thus the firm's average revenue curve.*¹¹

$$AR(Q) = TR(Q)/Q$$

where Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
AR is the average revenue
TR is the total revenue

$$MR(Q) = \Delta TR(Q) / \Delta Q$$

where MR is the marginal revenue
TR is the total revenue
Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
 ΔQ is the change in quantity produced (demanded)

¹⁰ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 340.

¹¹ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 341.

Profit maximization for a monopoly occurs when the cost of producing the next unit reaches a value equivalent to the revenue received by that unit. Of course, this is true for any product type. What makes a monopoly different is that the demand curve for a monopoly is also its average revenue curve and its marginal revenue curve is modified accordingly.

Average revenue must be greater than the average variable cost (AVC) for the monopoly to continue production [Quirk, 1987].

If output is such that $MR > MC$, then profits can be increased by increasing output; if output is such that $MR < MC$, then profits can be increased by decreasing output. It is only when $MR = MC$ that profits are maximized... As in the case of the competitive firm, there are certain qualifications to the marginal-cost-equals-marginal-revenue rule. The monopolist will produce a positive output only if he can cover his variable costs. If price is so low that it is less than average variable costs, then the profit-maximizing output is zero units--the monopolist will shut down his plant. This outcome can arise only if the demand curve is below the AVC curve at every output level...The profit-maximizing decision is to close the plant when $AR < AVC$ for every output level. If there is any output level at which $AR > AVC$, then the firm will continue operating at a positive output level, since its losses are less than its fixed costs.¹²

A monopoly's demand for resources is the same as that for any other product type, since the product type is only descriptive of a manufacturer's output, not the inputs that support it.

...So long as the monopolist deals in competitive input markets, his demand curves for inputs are well defined...In choosing an input mix to produce a given level of output, the monopolist duplicates the actions of a cost-minimizing, perfectly competitive firm....Recall that profit maximizing implies that inputs are hired to the point where the last unit of an input is hired adds as much to revenue as it does to cost (the marginal revenue product of any input is set equal to its marginal cost). Thus for a perfectly competitive firm, capital and labor are each hired to the point where

¹² Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 344.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MRP}_K &= p \cdot \text{MP}_K = r \\ \text{MRP}_L &= p \cdot \text{MP}_L = w \end{aligned}$$

...The marginal revenue products for a monopoly are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MRP}_K &= \text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_K = (\Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q) (\Delta Q / \Delta K) \\ \text{MRP}_L &= \text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_L = (\Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q) (\Delta Q / \Delta L) \end{aligned}$$

Adding one unit of capital (with labor constant) increases output by an amount given by MP_K . By adding one unit to the output for the monopolist firm increases total revenue by the amount MR. Hence for the monopolist $\text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_K$ is the marginal revenue product of capital, and $\text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_L$ is the marginal revenue product of labor. It follows that, for a monopolist, inputs K and L are hired to the point where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MRP}_K &= \text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_K = (\Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q) (\Delta Q / \Delta K) \\ \text{MRP}_L &= \text{MR} \cdot \text{MP}_L = (\Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q) (\Delta Q / \Delta L) \end{aligned}$$

Given that the monopoly firm faces a downward-sloping demand curve, then we have seen that for every Q, $\text{MR}(Q) < p(Q)$. Thus the monopoly firm hires fewer units of labor and capital than it would if it treated its output price as constant, as perfectly competitive firms do, given that capital and labor are cooperative inputs.¹³

Revenue is maximum where the average revenue (the demand curve) has unit elasticity and the marginal revenue is zero (this is where the total revenue curve has zero slope). For small, finite changes in Q (i.e., ΔQ),

$$\text{MR} = \Delta \text{TR} / \Delta Q = (p \Delta Q + Q \Delta p) / \Delta Q = p + Q \Delta p / \Delta Q$$

where MR is the marginal revenue
p is the selling price
Q is the quantity produced (demanded)
TR is the total revenue

Marginal Revenue and Elasticity of Demand

¹³ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 346.

The relationship between quantity produced and revenue as a function of the quantity produced increases or decreases depending upon the elasticity of the demand curve; that is, how changeable is the quantity demanded of a product to the change in its selling price. If the demand is elastic, then increased quantity translates into increased marginal revenue (though lower selling price); an inelastic demand curve means that a increasing quantity translates to a decrease in marginal revenue (and a lower selling price); if the demand curve is unit elastic, changes in quantity causes no change in marginal revenue [Quirk, 1987].

Moreover, viewing the total revenue (TR) curve for a product, three possibilities are evident for its slope that correspond directly to the product's elasticity of demand. That is, a zero slope indicates a unit elasticity of demand; a negative slope, an elasticity of demand that is less than one; a positive slope, an elasticity greater than one [Chacholiades, 1986].

there are *markets in ownership claims to resources*. Consumers buy and sell titles to various resources among themselves...there is the *rental market for resource services* in which the use of a resource such as land is made available to someone else for a specified period of time...there is the *market for newly produced resources*.¹⁴

These “newly produced resources” are “capital goods” (i.e., goods that are *manufactured for* production use rather than occurring in nature), ready to be exploited by other goods (products).

Exchanges between producers and consumers of goods are naturally enabled by markets. The market price of goods are determined by exchanges and interactions of buyers and sellers, by the number of goods made, bought, and sold[Quirk, 1987].

¹⁴ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 24.

Manufacturing is then a market that facilitates exchanges between products, acting as buyers and sellers of goods (resources), and these interactions determine the prices of products and the costs of resources by virtue of the quantities demanded and consumed.

The price elasticity of demand, η , is an important indicator in microeconomics since it shows the responsiveness to price of the quantity demanded of a product. η can be elastic, in-elastic, or unity elastic and is derived by [Quirk, 1986][Chacholiades, 1987]:

$$\eta = \frac{\text{price}}{\text{Demand}(\text{price})} \cdot \frac{d\text{Demand}(\text{price})}{d\text{price}}$$

Where $d\text{Demand}$ is the derivative of the demand curve,
 $\text{Demand}(\text{price})$
 price is the product selling price
 $d\text{price}$ is the derivative of the price of the product

For finite changes in quantity, η , is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\eta &= (\Delta Q / \Delta p)(p/Q) \\ MR &= (\Delta p / \Delta Q)Q + p \\ (\Delta p / \Delta Q) &= (1/\eta)(p/Q) \\ MR &= (1/\eta)(p/Q)Q + p = p(1/\eta + 1)\end{aligned}$$

When $\eta = -1$, $MR = 0 \leftarrow$ unit elastic demand
 When $-1 < \eta < 0$, $MR < 0 \leftarrow$ inelastic demand
 When $\eta < -1$, $MR > 0 \leftarrow$ elastic demand

With a downward sloping demand curve, as with a monopoly or monopolist-competition, $\eta \leq 0$; therefore the marginal revenue is less than the selling price ($MR < P$) for a monopoly or monopolistic-competition or any product type with a downward sloping average revenue curve [Quirk].

Demand is *inelastic* when η is between 0 and -1: a 1% change in prices causes < 1% change in demand (demand does not respond significantly to price changes; i.e., the total spent on a quantity of product increases slightly as the price increases). Demand is *elastic* when η is between -1 and -infinity: a 1% change in prices causes > 1% change in demand (responds

significantly to price changes; i.e., the total spent on a quantity of product decreases significantly as the price increases). Demand is *unity elastic* when $\eta = -1$: a 1% change in prices causes a 1% change in demand (responds equally to changes in price; i.e., the total spent on a quantity of product decreases in direct proportion to price increases) [Quirk, 1986][Chacholiades, 1987].

Expenditures (E) for a product change according to the price elasticity of demand:

$$dE = dprice \cdot [\eta + 1]$$

Where dE and dprice are derivatives of the product expenditure and price

A product's elasticity of demand increases when there are other products that can substitute for it, although allowing for lower price, this yields greater demand, thus potentially increased revenue.

the demand for a good is perfectly elastic when there is another good that is a perfect substitute for the first good.

In empirical work, to simplify measurement and estimation it is often assumed that the demand curve has a constant elasticity. That is, elasticity of demand is assumed to be the same for every price. A constant elasticity demand curve may be written as $D(p) = Bp^\alpha$, where α is the (constant) elasticity of demand and B is a constant whose value depends on other prices, income, and the other variables affecting demand.¹⁵

However, assuming a constant elasticity is useful only when variations of quantity for a product are small.

¹⁵ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 45.

Microeconomic theory includes the idea that, even if consumers have a certain level of capital earmarked for them at certain prices, they may, at other price levels, tend to purchase competing products exclusively. This idea takes form in the notions of *normal* and *inferior* goods. A normal good is a product that continues in demand as the available capital of the consumer increases. An *inferior* good is a product that has less demand as available consumer capital increases [Brown, 1992]. For example, at a lower level of corporate income, a manufacturer may choose to use most of the capital allocated for storage to rent space and a small amount to buy a few (relatively expensive, but convenient) mobile storage units. At a larger level of corporate income, the manufacturer may instead eliminate the use of rental storage entirely and buy several mobile units. Rental space is an inferior good and the mobile storage a normal good.

Within manufacturing, products are viewed as goods that support the owning firms profit. That is, products are inputs that manufacturing transforms into outputs that take the form of profits. Some products may be normal goods, always providing profit regardless of quantities produced and regardless of the competing products being manufactured. Other products may be inferior goods that provide a level of profit for small quantities, but less profit than a competing product at some higher quantity of production. Often, a product that is a normal good may substitute for a product that behaves as an inferior good to the overall profit of a manufacturing system.

...if output is held constant (along any isoquant), then the more units of a given input employed in production, the easier it is to substitute other inputs for the input.

The assumption that isoquant bound convex sets is equivalent to the *law of diminishing marginal rate of technical substitution*:

Along any production isoquant, the marginal rate of technical substitution of capital for labor decreases as the amount of labor increases.

To put this law in simpler terms, along any production isoquant, capital becomes a better substitute for labor as more units of labor are employed. This law describes the way that the marginal products of capital and labor behave along any isoquant.

Let ΔX = the change in the output brought about by changes in ΔL in labor and ΔK in capital. Then

$$\Delta X = MP_L \Delta L + MP_K \Delta K$$

that is, the change in output equals the increase in output that is due to adding one unit of labor (MP_L) times the number of units of labor added (ΔL) plus the increase in output that is due to adding one unit of capital (MP_K) times the number of units of capital added (ΔK). But along any isoquant, $\Delta X = 0$. It thus follows that

$$-\frac{\Delta K}{\Delta L} = \frac{MP_L}{MP_K}$$

or, equivalently,

$$MRTS = \frac{MP_L}{MP_K}$$

along any isoquant. Hence the marginal rate of technical substitution of capital for labor equals the ratio of the marginal product of labor to the marginal product of capital. The law of diminishing marginal rate of technical substitution thus asserts that, as we increase the amount of labor employed along an isoquant, the ratio of the marginal product of labor to the marginal product of capital falls.¹⁶

¹⁶ Quirk, James P. *Intermediate Microeconomics, Third Edition*, Science Research Associates, Chicago, Illinois 1987, 159.

APPENDIX I

Goal Program Listings

The software used to execute the following Linear Programs (goal programs) is: Linear Programming software used in this example is MORS Version 1.3 , Copyright, 1987, 1989, 1990 by G. Curry, B. Deuermeyer and R. Feldman.

Listing 1

The initial Linear Program:

```
MAX Z=U1 +U2 +U3 +U4 +O1 +O2 +O3 +O4
ST
  P1 -1.124*P2 -U1 +O1 = 0
-0.8897*P1+P2 -U2 +O2 = 0
-1.2345*P1 +P3 -U3 +O3 = 0
-2.2897*P1 +P4 -U4 +O4 = 0

  P1 >= 7.25 (COST OF PRODUCT #1)
  P1 <= 100
  P2 >= 6.45 (COST OF PRODUCT #2)
  P2 <= 100
  P3 >= 8.95 (COST OF PRODUCT #3)
  P3 <= 100
  P4 >= 16.6 (COST OF PRODUCT #4)
  P4 <= 100
  U1 >= -0.01 (ALL UNDER AND OVERFLOWS WITHIN A PENNY)
  U1 < 0
  U2 >= -0.01
  U2 < 0
  U3 >= -0.01
  U3 < 0
  U4 >= -0.01
  U4 < 0
  O1 >= 0
  O1 < 0.01
  O2 >= 0
  O2 < 0.01
  O3 >= 0
  O3 < 0.01
  O4 >= 0
  O4 < 0.01
```

Simplex Method

```
          ^^^ Optimal Solution ^^^
Z          =          0.0210
```


O3 >= 0
 O3 < 0.01
 O4 >= 0
 O4 < 0.01

Simplex Method

^^^ Optimal Solution ^^^

Z	=	0.0222
U1	=	0.0000
U2	=	0.0000
U3	=	0.0000
U4	=	0.0000
O1	=	0.0100
O2	=	0.0000
O3	=	0.0100
O4	=	0.0022
P1	=	9.5000
P4	=	21.7770
P2	=	8.4625
P3	=	11.7278
Surpl5	=	2.2500
Surpl7	=	2.0125
Slack8	=	91.5375
Surpl9	=	2.7778
Slack10	=	88.2722
Surpl11	=	5.1770
Slack12	=	11.6130
Slack13	=	0.0100
Slack15	=	0.0100
Slack17	=	0.0100
Slack19	=	0.0100
Slack22	=	0.0100
Slack24	=	0.0078

Compile time: 0.22 (Secs.)
 Run time : 0.33 (Secs.)